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LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES AND RESILIENCIES OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS: BASIS FOR IMPROVED ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE AND GOVERNANCE

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NATIONAL UNIVERSITY BULACAN

SCHOOL OF EDUCATION, ARTS AND SCIENCES

**LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES AND RESILIENCIES OF
SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS: BASIS FOR IMPROVED
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE
AND GOVERNANCE**

A Dissertation Manuscript Presented to the Faculty of the Graduate Studies
College of Education, Arts & Sciences
National University, Baliwag

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the
Degree of Doctor of Education
Major in Educational Management

John Marie E. Malco

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APPROVAL SHEET

In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of **DOCTOR OF EDUCATION MAJOR IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT** academic year 2024-2025, entitled “**LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES AND RESILIENCIES OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS: BASIS FOR IMPROVED ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE AND GOVERNANCE**” has been prepared and submitted by **John Marie E. Malco** who is hereby recommended for the corresponding ORAL EXAMINATION.

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DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to my late father, +Ernesto, a great example of resilience.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines leadership competencies and resiliencies of school administrators as basis for enhancing organizational performance and governance. Employing a mixed-method approach, the research encompasses quantitative data from a survey of 67 school administrators with qualitative insights from comprehensive interviews. The results reveal a high level of leadership competencies among administrators, specifically in advising, managing, leading, and relating. Additionally, the qualitative findings highlight that these administrators demonstrate a level of resilience, an essential attribute for effectively addressing the complexities and challenges inherent to education administration. The convergence of leadership competencies and resiliencies underscores the efficacy of school administrators to effectively enhance school governance. The study findings emphasize the important role of competent leadership and resiliency in sustaining effective organizational performance and governance. Statistical analysis rejects the null hypothesis which underscores the positive relationship between leadership competencies and resilience, implying that school administrators with strong leadership competencies have a stronger ability to foster organizational success and manage difficult circumstances. Based on these findings, the study proposes a comprehensive training and development program for school administrators. This program aims to further enhance their leadership skills and resilience, leading to improved organizational performance and governance. This study provides valuable insights into the critical role of leadership and resilience in education administration.

Keywords: Leadership Competencies, Resilience, School Administrators, Organizational Performance and Governance, Training Program

CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

This section presents the context of the study in resilient leadership and leadership competency. It aims to align the research objectives with the research questions.

Introduction

The functions, responsibilities, and duties of an education leader are extensive. Recent studies have focused on how school administrators can improve school performance (Khanal, Perry, & Park, 2020). It highlights the value of a school leader's position to identify important duties and demands that they must prioritize. Given that leaders are required to inspire a sense of engagement and commitment within their effective support to its employee growth and direct the organization toward a goal, the contribution of an effective leaders to the success of the organization is likely to be crucial during times of crisis. The significant event of the 21st century is the birth of modern ideas and technologies, specifically the electronic digital computers development. Much more with the emergence of the new normal education, the pandemic brings impact and already affecting the educational enterprise in significant ways. As cited in the study of Dumulescu and Muțiu (2021), the unforeseen obstacles of the recent pandemic forced school leaders to be flexible and adaptable. The breakout of COVID-19 pandemic puts a lot of strain on school principals to keep school governance effective (Pedroso et al., 2021).

In time of threat, challenges, and uncertainties, the directive of the Department of Education Secretary of the Philippines to ensure the health, safety and welfare of all learners, teachers, principals, school heads, and personnel of the department, while also finding ways for the improvement of learning. The Department of Education seek the understanding, support, and solidarity of the entire bureaucracy and all its stakeholders in the true spirit of unity and bayanihan or mutual help. The bureau emphasized to improve the learning system in the country and implemented the MATATAG curriculum which

focuses on foundational skills, intensification of values education and peace education, and the welfare of every Filipino learner (DM 054, 2023).

Many educational leaders took a huge responsibility in managing school operation, challenging situation, performing a variety of jobs, initiating reforms, and adjusting policies inside their school community, while negotiating systemic limitations and scarce resources (Burch et al., 2020). Its catastrophic effect on health and associated limitations have significantly affected the circumstances of individuals and groups (Marzana et al., 2021), including education. Global pandemics have historically been a catalyst for social, economic, and cultural change, and COVID-19 did the same (Eisenberg & Mordechai, 2020). This includes implementing cost-cutting strategies such as staff cutbacks, furloughs, and shortened work hours to the workforce schedules (Kuenzi et al., 2021). Furthermore, Bozkurt et al. (2020) cited in his study that many educational institutions were forced to shut down, and those that remained in operation had to drastically change their normal teaching methods. This change sped up the transformation of the traditional educational landscape to digitalization (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2021). It also pushed millions of educators to take part into online learning just to continue providing education in an alternative modality (Schechter et al., 2022). This change in educational setting and learning approach was a challenge for school administrators.

Resilience is a critical issue in leadership. Understanding it is more crucial because of the rapid changes in social, political, and economic conditions like war, terrorism, recession (King & Rothstein., 2010), as well as global pandemics (Eisenberg & Mordechai, 2020). It was thought that studying the crisis' effects on leaders would uncover important changes that influenced organizations both during and after the crisis (Knowles et al., 2019). The perspectives of the resilience, leadership, and of how the crisis has affected the performance of school administrators are the subjects of this study. Resilience is the ability to bounce back and maintain adequate behavior not only in the face of difficulty but also in emotional distress. This quality of overcoming hardship and unfavorable circumstances is a necessary quality for an effective leader.

The idea of resilience is essential to understand how individuals overcome hardship (Hartmann & Jüpner, 2020). As of now, it has been discovered that the concept

of resilient leadership is applicable in several contexts which includes the educational system (Dumulescu & Muțiu, 2021). Study finding of school principal's leadership strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic emerged in three findings which are strengths-based, values-based, and needs-based practices (Pedroso et al., 2021). Clearly, leadership emerged as a special strength, enabling the delegation of some responsibility and some continuity of decision-making within already-established networks in the school communities and, in turn, fostering the creation of community resilience (Beauchant et al., 2021).

There have been many studies on competency development and assessment that focusses on various fields and professions (Brundiars et al., 2021). Competencies are a person's general aptitudes and skills that enable them to successfully carry out the duties of a particular job. These competencies include personal qualities which are necessary for the success of a specific industry, organization, or field of work. Applying the idea in leadership and managerial perspective, leadership competencies are a collection of knowledge, skills, and abilities that work together to form an organization's effective leadership (Ngayo Fotso, 2021). The idea of competencies has brought a substantive impact in recruiting, selecting, developing, and managing supervisory positions (Wong, 2020). Recent research has found on how principals can improve school performance (Khanal et al., 2019), the cultural impact on school leaders' decision making (Truong et al., 2017), and the connection between leadership styles and followers' resilience (Sommer et al., 2015). However, there hasn't been much empirical research done on the relationship between leadership competencies and resilient leadership. Addressing the research gap, this study explored leadership competencies and resilience of school administrators.

Theoretical Framework

The concept of transformative leadership is fundamental to the theoretical framework of resilient leadership competencies and its effects on organizational performance and governance. According to the theory of transformational leadership, leaders that empower, encourage, and inspire their subordinates cultivate greater levels of engagement, creativity, and productivity in their businesses (Northouse, 2021).

Transformative theories of leadership are strongly aligned with resilient leadership, which includes the capacity to handle adversity, create flexibility, and retain a positive view in the face of adversities. This study is also anchored to the resilience theory developed by Garmezy (1991). Research suggest that resilient leaders not only motivate their teams to be more committed, confident, and trusting of one another during times of crisis or adversity, but also enhance organizational performance (Madi Odeh, 2023). Resilient leaders demonstrate emotional intelligence, agility, and strategic foresight—qualities necessary for efficient governance (Ho et al., 2023). Leaders may improve organizational resilience, sustainability, and agility by incorporating resilience into their leadership style. This ultimately led to better governance and performance outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

The study seeks to determine effect of leadership competencies in the resilience in organizational performance and governance. The degree of resilience that people exhibit in an organizational setting is the dependent variable, while leadership qualities are proposed as the independent variable that shape this level of resilience. Resilience is the ability to withstand hardship, trauma, outside shocks, or any major cause of stress while growing from them and getting ready for the future (Giustiniano et al., 2016). Resilient people are more able to handle stress, adjust to change, and keep a good attitude in which all these qualities are necessary for effective leadership. A person's ability to lead and influence people toward the accomplishment of organizational goals is reflected in their leadership competencies, which are a variety of abilities, characteristics, and actions (Northouse, 2021). Resilient people who exhibit flexibility, persistence, and constructive coping mechanisms develop and improve these capabilities, which include strategic thinking, communication skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making abilities (Singha, 2024; Skinner et al., 2020). The attributes that are necessary for strengthening the influence of organizations that have the willingness to commit themselves to developing employee and organizational resilience via leadership development.

The researcher investigated how leadership competencies affects the resilience of the organizations' performance and governance which in turn affects the efficacy of

leadership and organizational outcomes. Employing this conceptual framework, the researcher identified its effects to the efficacy of leadership and organizational outcomes.

The figure below shows the input-process-output that the researchers has applied in this study. The researcher first identified the leadership competencies of school administrators in terms of advising, managing, leading, and relating. Moreover, the researcher measures the level of resilience of school administrators, identified the challenges faced by the school administrators, converged the quantitative and qualitative data, and identified the effects of leadership competencies in the resilience of organizational performance and governance. The process includes the identification of respondents and analysis of data through questionnaire survey, informal interview, and statistical treatment. The expected output is a training program in sustaining effective organizational performance and governance.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

To gain a deeper knowledge of leadership and resilience in organizational performance and governance, the researcher believes that the case of the school administrators of the Department of Education sector can be informative. This study aims to determine the leadership competencies and resiliencies of school administrators as a basis for improved organizational performance and governance.

Specifically, this seeks to answer the following:

1. How may leadership competencies of school administrators be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 advising;
 - 1.2 managing;
 - 1.3 leading; and
 - 1.4 relating?
2. How may the resilience of school administrators be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 ability to adapt change;
 - 2.2 ability to deal with what comes along;
 - 2.3 ability to cope with stress;
 - 2.4 ability to stay focused and think clearly;
 - 2.5 ability to not get discouraged in the face of failure; and
 - 2.6 ability to handle unpleasant feelings such as anger, pain or sadness?
3. What are the primary challenges identified by school administrators?
4. What are the common themes and findings found in the convergence of data presented?
5. Do school administrators' leadership competencies affect the resilience in organizational performance and governance?
6. What training program be established for sustaining effective organizational performance and school governance?

Hypothesis of the Study

School administrators' leadership competencies do not significantly affect resilience in organizational performance and governance.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of leadership competencies of school administrators to the resilience of organizational performance and governance. It investigated the specific traits associated with leadership competencies and resilience in the context of school governance and explored how school administrators handle challenges, crises, and uncertainties. The study was confined only to the Department of Education, Division of City of Malolos, Bulacan.

The findings of the study were limited to the specific context of the study and may not be universally applicable to all educational settings since it relied on perceptions and opinions of individuals regarding resilient leadership, which may be subjective and vary among different stakeholders. The study was also limited by time constraints, preventing in-depth longitudinal analysis of the sustained impact of resilient leadership over an extended period. External factors such as economic conditions, government policies, or global events may influence school governance independently of resilient leadership and are beyond the scope of this study. This study was also delimited to include only elementary and secondary school administrators of the Department of Education-Region III, City Schools Division of Malolos, City of Malolos, Bulacan.

Significance of the Study

This research is important for school administrators because the study will provide essential information about school education leadership and management.

School Administrators. The results of this study can help the school administrators with the planning and execution of teacher leadership development initiatives. Present and future school leaders can be better prepared to handle the challenges of educational governance by incorporating resilience-focused training into their curriculum. To guarantee that high-quality instruction is continued in the face of outside obstacles, it is essential to comprehend how resilient leadership practices support stable school governance.

Education Policy Makers/Accreditors. Education systems are subject to frequent reforms and policy modifications. Effectively responding to the shifts of the education system will enable leaders to maintain school governance in line with changing requirements and standards for education. With the newfound understanding, policymakers can design frameworks that support the emergence and use of resilient leadership in the context of school governance.

Resource Manager. Resilient leadership can improve how well resources are used in schools. Effective leaders will be able to manage resources wisely and foster sustainability and long-term success by navigating resource limitations and uncertainties.

Community Linkages Officer. Resilient leaders frequently establish enduring alliances with the local community. Comprehending the significance of resilience in leadership can aid in formulating tactics that promote community involvement and endorsement of educational endeavors, establishing a mutually beneficial association between educational institutions and their surrounding communities.

Crisis Managers. Natural disasters and societal issues are just two of the many crises that schools may encounter. Leaders that possess resilience are better able to manage emergencies and protect the health and safety of employees and students. This research can shed light on crisis management techniques in relation to school governance.

Teachers. Positive school cultures boost teacher morale, and resilient leaders help to foster those cultures. It is imperative to comprehend the relationship between resilience leadership and teacher satisfaction and retention to cultivate a stable and motivated teaching staff, which in turn improves student outcomes.

Students. The learning environment is directly impacted by resilient leadership. Leaders who place a high priority on resilience foster a climate of positivity and support that improves student wellbeing and academic achievement. This research can clarify the connection between enhanced student outcomes and resilient leadership.

Future Researchers. This study adds to the larger body of educational research by examining the role resilient leadership plays in maintaining school governance. It offers a starting point for further research on resilience, governance, and the efficacy of leadership in educational settings.

Definition of Terms

Various definitions were incorporated to give context to the study:

Educational Leadership – Educational leadership is a discipline that is independent to management. The term is applied to school administrations that cultivate attitudes that strive to create positive change in educational policy and processes (Tosas, 2015).

Leadership – “the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives” (Hassan et al., 2013, p. 133).

Leadership Competencies – The basis for effectively completing tasks or reaching objectives that call for professional expertise including traits, self-concept, social role, knowledge, and skills (Gilli et al., 2022).

Organizational Performance – evaluation of employee’s behavior towards work assignment in an organization associated with the establishment of how best or poor an individual executed or accomplished a specific task (Kalogiannidis, 2021).

Resilience – A human capacity to meet adversity. Resilience is the ability of a person to respond to circumstances that put them at significant risk while maintaining their normal ability to function (Bonanno, 2004).

Resilient Leadership – The ability to respond quickly to changing circumstances by adopting a dynamic combination of clear direction, preparedness, and flexibility (Lombardi et al., 2021).

School Administrators – professionals who carries administrative tasks which involves the management of all school operations. School administrators can be the school principal, assistant principal or head teachers as defined in the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (DO 024, 2020).

School Governance – It encompasses vision, strategy, accountability, trust, capacity, and stakeholder relationships (Leechman et al., 2019).

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter deals with the related literature and studies that focus on the important concepts regarding the various factors related to the leadership competencies of school administrators and resilience in the organizational performance and governance. In this chapter, several literatures and studies were conglomerated to give important background of the study.

Foreign Literature

Resilient Leadership

The word 'resilience' is derived from the Latin word 'resilire,' which means to leap, jump, or bounce back (Ma et al., 2018). Since its conception in 1973, resilience has changed across several disciplines and been defined in various ways (Moussa et al., 2020). Resilience is the ability to withstand hardship, trauma, outside shocks, or any major cause of stress while growing from them and getting ready for the future (Giustiniano et al., 2016). Scholars concur to the idea that resilience is a complex and nuanced word that may be used to measure people's ability to handle stress and hardship despite the many meanings (Kimhi et al., 2020). Resilience is often used to describe organization or individuals that can recover from a strain or abrupt changes without a major effect on its function (Linnenluecke, 2015).

Moreover, resilient leadership has been shown to be relevant in several foreign studies for several situations. As an example, Linnenluecke (2015) study describes the evolution and knowledge gaps in resilience research in business and management. Furthermore, Crane and Searle (2016) study investigated how specific stressors can foster resilience in the workplace. Williams et al. (2017) also mentioned in their study that research on resilience has attempted to describe how individuals and organizations prepare for and overcome adversity. It also suggests that being resilient is the aptitude in adapting to change or modifications (Giustiniano et al., 2016). Hence, it is believed that fostering adaptability is a unique leadership responsibility that would allow the company to adjust

operations in response to shifting conditions (Karreinen, et al., 2023). Resilient leadership is indeed significant for the school leaders in how they manage and lead the school despite the challenges and circumstances in their workplace (Pangandoyon et al., 2024).

A review of the literature on the three leadership theories revealed that traits covered by the resilient leadership theory—such as emotional intelligence, learning, performance orientation, adaptation/change orientation, and collective leadership—are already considered by the transformational–transactional leadership theories, meaning they are redundant when looking for the best leadership strategy (Dartey-Baah, 2015). Resilience factors are dynamic capabilities, workforce diversity, effective communication with stakeholders, sustainable resilience practice, change management, organizational flexibility, team empowerment, agile leadership, technology capability and innovation ambidexterity (Sreenivasan et al., 2023).

The value of being resilient is critical in leadership since leaders are required to make decisions which involve some degree of risk. This competency is relevant to organizational leaders' personal growth and transformation (King & Rothstein, 2010). The value of being resilient is also being studied in different disciplines. A study in business resilience, Aldianto et al. (2021) provided a resilience framework by exploring capability, behavior, and knowledge in a startup business. It implies that a resilient business will constantly find ways to take risks and capitalize on opportunities. Furthermore, Camiel et al. (2022) study on understanding leadership effectiveness in the wake of challenges implies that the role of a leader in reconstruction is essential and leadership qualities such as readiness, adaptability, resilience, and power of example.

In Kim and Windsor (2015) study on resilience and work-life balance, it explored how first-line nurse managers constructed the meaning of resilience and its relationship to work-life balance for nurses in Korea. Haver et al. (2014) also cited in how seasoned general managers control their emotions when faced with challenging leadership responsibilities. Cooke et al. (2021) also argued that employee resilience is crucial to organizations wishing to manage their mergers and acquisitions successfully. Furthermore, Koliou et al. (2020) denotes that community resilience enables a community to govern itself to withstand changes and catastrophes. The said study also implies that

leadership is a key component of community resilience. Those who are not prepared with the necessary resilience and coping capabilities are more disposed to encounter negative mental and psychological outcomes (Labrague et al., 2021). Conversely, those who are more resilient and have more effective coping strategies can adapt to life changes and difficulties and keep functioning well - physically, psychologically, and mentally. Resilience is becoming more well-known in the management literature while paying little attention to effects from the workplace (Kossek and Perrigino, 2016).

In Extremera et al. (2022) study on resilient leadership involves leading in the face of adversity because it is crucial for school principals to exercise effective leadership and develop the ability to adapt to new circumstances and overcome challenges. This suggests that different resilience strategies must be employed by leaders depending on the temporal demands associated with the persistence of adversity (Förster, 2023). Furthermore, Ashfaq (2022) cited in his study that employees can overcome their experience of varying levels of engagement when they have resilient leadership. Developing increased self-confidence, teamwork, communication and problem-solving abilities, empathy and compassion, humility, thankfulness, hardiness, persistence, and patience were among the resilience factors that each leader possessed on an individual basis (Vito et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the study of Day et al. (2020) emphasizes the significance of aligning leadership actions with organizational goals to improve school outcomes. Moreover, the study of Harahap et al. (2022) points out that teachers and school principal's resilience is developed through the concrete action of the principals in facilitating response to challenges. Similarly, the study of Lynch et al. (2023), it features the leader's capacity to make professional learning decision that supports the professional learning needs of their teachers. This evaluation supports the study of Darling-Hammond and Cook-Harvey (2018) emphasizes the role of leadership in creating supportive environments that facilitate student learning and development. Strategies like problem solving and collaboration are crucial in teacher resilience.

The impact of communication significantly creates solidarity among school leaders, teachers, students, and stakeholders. Syakur et al. (2020) point out the importance of communication skills in leadership and its impact on organizational performance.

Similarly, Edwards-Groves et al. (2020) study also highlights the importance of dialogue in educational leadership and its role in building trust and credibility.

Organizational Resilience

Resilience, at the organizational level, is the confluence of traits, skills, competencies, or abilities that enable an organization to endure known and unidentified disruptions while continuing to function (Ruiz-Martin et al., 2018). According to recent studies of Anderson et al. (2019), Duchek (2019), and Li (2020), organizational resilience is the aptitude, ability, or competency of an organization to anticipate, deal with, adapt to, and learn from negative events. The relationship between employee resilience and organizational resilience has been acknowledged by contemporary scholars (Kuntz et al., 2017). Furthermore, organizational resilience has been defined by several authors. For instance, Ma et al. (2018) defined organizational resilience as the ability to recover from adversity and obstacles and is known as organizational resilience. Others define resilience as the ability of the business to endure, adjust, and expand in a changing and unpredictable environment. Hence, organizational resilience is the "ability" or "capacity" of the organization to respond to changes in the environment, foresee, adapt, and draw lessons from past coping mechanisms (Moran, 2016).

Organizational culture and resilient leadership are important mediators of the model employed in the study of Hendrik et al. (2022). It suggests the from the perspective of practical significance, organizational resilience and resilient leadership are most strongly correlated. Organizational resilience includes the interaction between organization, its stakeholders, and the environment when faced with adversity (Williams et al., 2017). Even though resilience in organizations has garnered interest recently, there is still more research that needs to be conducted to add more knowledge of this crucial field of study (Fisher et al., 2018).

Organizational Performance and Governance

Crisis causes unexpected, fundamental disruptions to school function with potentially serious consequences for the organization, its stakeholders, and its reputation

(Grissom and Condon, 2021). This suggests that people who possess more resilience and more useful coping mechanisms can adjust to changes in their lives and maintain their quality of life (Labrague et al., 2021). Considering the inherent difficulty of handling crises in a command-and-control strategy, Williams et al. (2017) stated that organizational leaders, as well as school leaders, should build resilience to have a strong desire to create new standards as well as the capacity to do so. Resiliency according to King and Rothstein (2010) study, is considered as important both career recovery and ongoing professional success. In support of this, Näswall (2019) states that any company's existence and performance are heavily reliant on the resilience of both the organization and its personnel. Improvisation is also important as stated by Lombardi et al. (2021) study because it upholds the system's reliance; that is, due to its indirect effects on the social infrastructure in addition to its direct ones. The idea of resilience emphasizes the need of improving any system's capacity to withstand disturbances (Sahebjamnia et al., 2018).

In a similar scoping review, Striepe and Cunningham (2021) redefined leadership in K–12 schools during times of crisis based on the identification of critical factors that influence how much school leadership responds to school crises across the year 2010–2020 period. Several schools in the Philippines were struggling to survive even before the COVID-19 outbreak. For instance, some schools have seen varying degrees of revenue erosion as a result of educational innovations (such the creation and implementation of the K12 program). Inadequate preparedness for this change put educational institutions in a challenging position, and the process of transitioning had a significant impact on the organization's capacity to develop and remain viable (Näswall et al., 2019). The primary administrative issues faced by school K-12 administrators have also been examined in a study of K–12 school leadership in times of crisis (Parveen et al., 2022). The said study implies that the challenges include learning continuity, safety during school re-opening, and self-care, emotional and mental wellness of students and teachers, equitable leadership, high standards of education gaps, digital divisions, and cyber security.

Furthermore, in Adam's et al (2021) study, school leaders report that there is a scarcity of technical resources to enhance students' learning, which made it more difficult for them to figure out how to continue teaching and learning at a high level while doing

so remotely. Similar results were found in two comparable research that were done in Turkish educational contexts (Kavrayici & Kesim, 2021) and in the USA (Brion & Kiral, 2021), respectively, where school administrators elaborated on the technical issues they encountered in the following situations. First, for instructional and communication objectives in the usage and administration of virtual online learning platforms. Second, it revealed issues related to internet connectivity and a lack of bandwidth in homes with many pupils by examining the quality of school internet infrastructure. The study of Rajesh (2022) offered a framework for decision support for to be used by executives to comprehend, gauge, and enhance the level of resilience in industrial supply chains.

A component identified as a significant barrier to effective educational leadership in many educational institutions around the world during the COVID-19 pandemic was lack of adequate funding. Socio-economic disparities were also cited by school leaders (Kavrayici & Kesim, 2021; Lien et al., 2022). In Brion and Kiral's (2021) study, reveals that lack of financing was the main factor that prompted K–12 school administrators to use their creativity and look for alternate sources of income to provide staff members with online professional development.

The pandemic era forced school administrators in a distant, rural community in Central Jamaica to increase their communication skills through training to reestablish and improve school-community interactions at the post-crisis stage (Bent-Cunningham & Mauzard, 2021). To improve school-level operations and address mental health issues that were made worse by the pandemic in their educational institutions during the recovery phase, Banerjee-Batist et al.'s study (2022) stresses that educational leaders were observed to reconsider and restructure initial ideas and plans in favor of alternative methods and practices. In Coquyt (2021) study, for superintendents to improve their flexibility and adaptability in decision-making and to improve their communication with all interested parties by being more transparent and routinely seeking stakeholder feedback, superintendents can hone their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The capacity for critical decision-making in the face of uncertainty, self-control, and communication responses to the redesigned framework for leadership competencies (Camiel et al., 2022).

Resilient organizations require resilient leadership as a precondition at the organizational level. The recent pandemic significantly changes the performance of numerous organizations, organizations need to be resilient to be flexible and sensitive to a variety of changing circumstances (Pandita et al., 2023). The study of Suryaningtyas et al, (2022) shows a positive correlation between organizational performance and organizational resilience. Organizational values influenced the choice of situation-appropriate leadership styles to support employees (Tvedt et al., 2023). In the same study of Suryaningtyas et al, (2022), emphasized the role of leaders to apply organizational resilience consistently, both strategically and operationally, to ensure the company's sustainability. Makoe (2023) highlighted that strong leaders who can adapt to changing circumstances and learn new skills are essential to the long-term viability of distance education.

The importance of incorporating sustainability into educational curricula has been highlighted by recent research. According to scholars, students' comprehension of social and environmental issues is improved when sustainability concepts are integrated into various subject areas (Gray et al., 2019). Experiential learning and project-based learning have been found to be successful approaches for getting students interested in sustainability education (Kohl et al., 2022). There is clear evidence that principals in school play management and leadership roles that determine how well schools function (Extremera et al, 2022).

Several studies show that to achieve long-term corporate survival, corporate sustainability, organizational resilience, and corporate purpose combine (Florez-Jimenez, 2024). In practice, it offers a tool for sustainable development by offering a framework to analyze sustainable value in a range of business models as a basis for improvement in sustainability. Theoretically, it structures value concepts to help better understand the sustainable value process in business models (Méndez-León, 2021). By setting an example of dedication, providing direction to subordinates, and exercising cognitive vigilance while at work, leaders can have an impact on the performance of their organizations (Narcikara & Zehir, 2016). Furthermore, emotional support and connection, teamwork and organizational culture, transparent communication, shared decision-making, a clear

mission and values statement, and a work-life balance are all factors that can foster organizational resilience and sustainability (Vito et al., 2022). The study of Lombardi et al., (2021) implies that managers need some crucial new information. Improvisation is significant because it sustains the system's dependability, which is due to both its direct and indirect effects on the social infrastructure.

Local Literature

Resilient Leadership

Scholarly reviews of resilience studies have garnered significant attention. A lot of empirical papers have been published in several significant journals. As an example, a study conducted by Valladolid (2021) investigates the relationships between college students' resilience and a few indicators of their general well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the moderating effect of coping strategies in these connections. The study confirms the positive relationship between resilience and well-being. Additionally, the same study discovered a positive correlation between approach coping strategy and resilience, suggesting that resilient people use constructive coping mechanisms. According to Ng, et al., (2020), leadership has a significant effect on community resilience. It points out the socioeconomic resources of the community and have a significant relationship with community resilience. Incorporating the residents' input into the community engagement programs is important in determining the impact of the pandemic (Gallespen et al., 2021). Moreover, the idea that community resilience can also be understood as the innate ability to adapt, survive, and rebuild in response to natural disturbances by utilizing its positive beliefs, values, characteristics, and practices (Adviento et al., 2010) as well as the qualitative indicators of resilience rooted in survival (Padrigo, 2022).

Resilience in the context of this study is felt by an individual following a traumatic event in their life. Being resilient serves as a springboard for comprehending the gratitude-experience process in life. Ignacio et al., (2017) investigated the mediating role of posttraumatic growth in predicting generalized gratitude of resilient PWDS. The outcomes indicate that posttraumatic growth mediates the relationship between the two variables and

that resilience does predict gratitude. The study demonstrates that PWDs' ability to bounce back from adversity doesn't impact their ability to feel thankful. Not only does resilience help people feel thankful, but it also fosters growth and helps them give meaning to their experiences after being disabled (Ignacio et al., 2017).

The idea of being resilient is to overcome hardship and the quality to overcome hardships. Bayaua (2022) confirmed that the recent pandemic presented several challenges for media professionals. However, these adversities helped them develop resilience and, in turn, maintain and adapt to carry out their mandate as sources of information during the pandemic. There really were widespread changes in the workplace during the Covid19 pandemic and business sustainability has been in the spotlight. However, business owners and employees showed resiliency which had a positive note on business sustainability (Buntigao et al., 2023).

On the other hand, Alarcon (2021) study on crisis leadership discusses that school leaders should recognize impending crisis warning signs and organize their responsive strategy. Leaders' ability to navigate a system fluidly and the ability of sensemaking during the global crisis are essential in sustaining the workflow of the organization. Work motivation and social support towards resilience among elementary public-school teachers was the focus of the study of Remedios (2020). The same study concluded that enhancing teachers' work performance requires a strong focus on work motivation, social support, and work resilience (Remedios, 2020). Resilience and emotional intelligence among teachers also show that the more emotionally intelligent a teacher is, the more resilient they are (Sencio, 2020). Dizon and de Guzman (2021) stressed in their study that principals overseeing schools in the Philippines suffer from the agony of not having access to the necessary suitable funding resources to be invested in streamlined operational procedures at schools and the acquisition of necessary technology infrastructure.

Synthesis

Resilience has been described and used in a variety of literatures which demonstrates that the theory is applicable in multiple fields. It is obvious that resilient leadership is necessary in the intricate and dynamic environments found in contemporary

organizations. Being able to overcome obstacles and lead with flexibility is now essential for leaders who must navigate complexity, uncertainty, and quick changes. Using information from multiple related studies, this synthesis looks at the intersection of resilient leadership and leadership competencies.

Several academic studies highlight the significance of resilient leadership in promoting organizational effectiveness and worker well-being. Resilient leaders show that they can withstand adversity, learn from mistakes, and inspire their teams to achieve even in the face of adversity. The capacity of a leader to proficiently lead their team towards the achievement of organizational objectives is linked to their possession of a collection of abilities, conduct, and attributes recognized as leadership competencies.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This chapter presents the research methodology employed in this study. This also includes the research design, respondents, instrumentation, data gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment which is performed in this study.

Methods and Techniques Used

The study utilized a mixed method design known as the Concurrent Triangulation Mixed Method Design. Mixed Method research design is a type of research design in which the researcher combines quantitative and qualitative research techniques, methods, approaches, concepts, or language into a single study to increase the breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration (Creswell & Clark, 2007). The research method combined, associated, and mixed the qualitative and quantitative data of the study (Creswell et al., 2003). A mixed-method research design is used the study in which it compares the variables that successful leaders demonstrate across various organizations they lead.

The study examined how school administrators manage issues and maintain successful educational management in a post-crisis phase by highlighting the connections between theoretical frameworks and associated studies on resilient leadership. Specifically, the concurrent mixed method was utilized in which the researcher converged quantitative and qualitative data to provide an in-depth study of the research problem (Creswell, 2011). The concurrent model collects quantitative and qualitative data separately at roughly the same time, and then the various results are converged or united during the interpretation. The goal of the triangular mixed methodology with a concurrent model is to give equal weight to quantitatively and qualitative data, to converge the results during interpretation, and to draw valid and well-substantiated conclusions about the research problem (Creswell & Clark, 2007).

To collect data for the quantitative research, the study will use survey questionnaire to assess the resiliency and leadership competencies of school

administrators. The researcher also employed a survey for resiliency and leadership competencies of school administrators to collect quantitative data. On the other hand, the researcher used a questionnaire for the interview to obtain accurate responses from the respondents for gathering the qualitative data through a face-to-face and online gathering procedure. The results of the data were the basis in developing the output of the study which a training framework and training program. The data was justified to use the concurrent mixed method technique to collect the respondents' in-depth response. The researcher avoided and eliminated research bias, which is why this approach is employed.

Respondents of the Study

This study utilized the homogenous purposive sampling technique which involved individuals that possess similar characteristics or attributes (Omona, 2013; Onwuegbuzie, 2015). Thus, the researcher purposely selected the respondents to maximize the understanding of the underlying phenomena of the study. The sample of this study includes 67 school administrators from various elementary and secondary schools of the Division of City of Malolos utilizing purposive homogeneous sampling method.

To ensure a thorough representation of leadership opinions and experiences, these people were selected based on their leadership roles and responsibilities. The respondents chosen to offer valuable perspectives on the various ways which resilience affects leadership effectiveness and organizational outcomes, along with insights into the relationship between resilient leadership competencies, organizational performance, and governance practices. The goal of homogeneous sampling is to select participants with comparable characteristics (Etikan et al., 2016). The objective is to extract perspectives and ideas from a particular group that possesses attributes. Yin (2016) adds on to state that even if a purposive sample might not be representative, it's still essential to incorporate sources that might give opinions that differ from those of many individuals.

Table 1: Respondents of the Study

School/District	Respondents
A	6
B	17
C	5
D	7
E	6
F	4
G	7
H	5
I	5
J	5
Total	67

Instruments of the Study

The researcher utilized the following research instruments and techniques in gathering data and information:

Connor Davidson Resilience Indicator Scale 25

Connor Davidson Resilience Scale (CD RISC) was utilized for data gathering in the first phase of this study. This instrument measures resilience or how well a person is equipped to bounce back after a stressful event, tragedy, or trauma. A letter of request for utilizing this tool was sent to the authors of CD RISC. CD RISC consists of 25 questions answered on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 – 4. Higher scores on the Likert scale indicate higher levels of resilience. The Cronbach's alpha for CD RISC is 0.89, while the test-retest reliability coefficient is 0.87 (Connor & Davidson, 2003). Moreover, the key component of the Connor Davidson resilience scale are a.) were categorized in the ability to adapt change (items 1, 8, 11, and 21), b.) ability to deal with what comes along the way (items 3, 4, 9, 20, and 24), c.) the ability to cope with stress (items 2, 7 and 13), d.) the ability to stay focused and think clearly (items 10, 14, 15 and 17), e.) the ability to not get

discouraged in the face of failure (items 5, 16, 18, 23, and 25), and f.) the ability to handle unpleasant feelings such as anger, pain or sadness (items 6, 12, and 19).

Connor and Davidson (2003) defined resilience as a measure of how to thrive in the face of adversity. They administered examples of CD RISC administered to the community, outpatients, and two PTSD clinical trials. The CD RISC was evaluated for reliability, validity, and the scale's logical structure. Sensitivity to treatment effects was examined from the clinical trials. The range demonstrated good psychometric properties, and factor analysis yielded five factors (Connor & Davidson, 2003).

Competency Evaluation Tool for School Leaders

The Competency Evaluation Tool for School Leaders is designed to assess the level of competency deemed to be necessary in the effective and efficient school governance and delivery of student services. A letter of request for utilizing this tool was sent to the author. The tool consists of 30 questions answered on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – 5 (Magat, 2019).

The areas of competency of this evaluation tool are a.) advising which includes the knowledge, skills and attitudes related to developing a high level of professional standards of quality counseling, coaching, and providing support and direction; b.) managing which includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for the realization of the vision, mission, and core values of the institution; c.) leading which includes the knowledge, skills and abilities required of a leader to work effectively, to envision, to plan, to effect change, and to address issues in and out of the organization; and.) relating which includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to interact with individuals and groups with diverse views.

Data Gathering Procedure

The primary data-gathering technique in this study was a questionnaire method to determine resiliency and leadership competencies in sustaining school governance effective performance. The study used a structured questionnaire adapted from the studies of Connor-Davidson (2003) and Magat (2019) for data collection that includes two parts,

namely, leaders' resilience scale, and leadership competency. Upon approval of the panel of experts on the proposed study, the researcher prepared a letter of request to conduct the study addressed to the School Division Superintendent.

Moreover, the researcher conducted the study to school administrators, including department heads, stationed in the different schools of the division of Malolos. The participants answered two questionnaires, namely, the leadership competency evaluation tool and the CD RISC. An interview was conducted after answering the said questionnaires.

Data Processing and Statistical Treatment

Upon the completion of data gathering, the researcher consolidated the responses of the two questionnaires. The descriptive statistics include the arithmetic means and standard deviations of each instrument. The responses were collated and encoded through various tables in Microsoft Excel and classification was identified in terms of dependent and independent variables in preparation for the statistical treatment. The statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 27 was used for the inferential statistical computation and treatment. A multiple regression analysis was also used to determine the relative effect of the variables. Additionally, the qualitative data were categorized into codes, and themes. The themes were extracted from the analysis using both automated and manual processes.

Furthermore, the researcher utilized the following statistical tools:

Weighted Mean. Weighted mean was used to determine the mean average ratings of the respondents assessing the resiliency and leadership competency.

Likewise, the following five-point Likert scale was utilized in determining the description evaluation of resiliency.

Table 2: Connor-Davidson Resilience 4-point Likert Scale

Rating Scale	Likert Scale Interval	Descriptive Evaluation
4	3.21 - 4.00	True Nearly All the Time
3	2.41 - 3.20	Often True
2	1.61 - 2.40	Sometimes True
1	0.81 - 1.60	Rarely True
0	0 - .80	Not True at All

The mean scores were interpreted as follows: True nearly all the time in the scale interval of 3.21-4.00, Often true in the scale interval of 2.41 - 3.20, Sometimes True in the scale interval of 1.61 - 2.40, Rarely True in the scale interval of 0.81 - 1.60, and Not True at All in the scale interval of 0 - .80.

Moreover, the researcher used the following five-point Likert scale in determining the description evaluation of leadership competency. The means were interpreted as follows: never in the scale interval of 1.00 - 1.80, Rarely in the scale interval of 1.81 - 2.60, Sometimes in the scale interval of 2.61 - 3.40, Often in the scale interval of 3.41 - 4.20, and Always in the scale interval of 4.21 - 5.00.

Table 3: Leadership Competencies 5-point Likert Scale

Rating Scale	Range	Descriptive Evaluation
1	1.00 - 1.80	Never
2	1.81 - 2.60	Rarely
3	2.61 - 3.40	Sometimes
4	3.41 - 4.20	Often
5	4.21 - 5.00	Always

Another statistical technique used in this study to investigate the effect leadership competencies on resiliency was multiple regression analysis. A deeper knowledge of the elements impacting organizational performance and governance is made possible by multiple regression analysis, which accounts for potential confounding variables and

evaluates the distinct contribution of each predictor variable. The researcher aims to get important insights for organizational strategy and leadership development by revealing the degree to which leadership qualities affect resiliency in governance practices and organizational performance using this statistical method.

Moreover, descriptive analysis was used to determine the levels of resilience exhibited by school leaders. The researcher was able to describe the respondent's level of resilience in terms of their overall resilience levels across various resilience characteristics by using descriptive statistics which include mean scores and standard deviations.

On the other hand, qualitative data analysis was also employed in this study to interpret qualitative data and understand what it represents. Particularly, thematic data analysis was used to determine meaning behind answer of the respondent. It involves identifying key themes in a large body of text. Thematic analysis identifies patterns of meaning or themes across a data set, enabling the research to make sense of phenomena and experience (Clarke & Braun, 2017). The first step undertaken by the researcher was structuring qualitative data by plotting it into a spreadsheet. After which, the researcher identified the set of codes, identified key words or phrases, and assigned the data to a category of meaning. These codes or categories represent topics or patterns of thinking (Rädiker & Kuckartz, 2020). The interview guide served as the basis for the generated codes, with the questions assigned to a category, in consideration of the study objectives and research questions.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this research, utmost attention has been given to ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. To uphold ethical standards, the researcher implemented robust data protection measure, such as anonymizing personal information and using secure storage systems. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, clearly outlining the purpose of the study, the potential risks, and the rights of the participants to withdraw at any stage without any adverse consequences.

Furthermore, ethical guidelines established by relevant institutional review boards and regulatory bodies were strictly adhered to throughout the research process. Any

potential implications of the findings on the privacy of individuals were thoroughly considered, and recommendations for safeguarding privacy in the healthcare sector was proposed with a focus on balancing technological advancements with ethical principles.

Additionally, the researcher acknowledged the potential biases that may arise in the interpretation of results and is committed to presenting a fair and objective analysis. It is essential to approach this study with sensitivity to the ethical implications of technology on individuals, and every effort has been made to minimize harm and prioritize the well-being and rights of the participants.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyses, and evaluates the data gathered through the study. To address the concurrent mixed method design, data analysis was divided into two parts that correspond to the quantitative and qualitative phases of data collection.

Level of Leadership Competencies of School Leaders

One way of determining the respondent's level of leadership competency of school leaders was to conduct a quantitative survey. The Competency Evaluation Tool for School Leaders was utilized in determining the level of respondents' leadership competencies. The instrument is designed to assess the level of competency deemed to be necessary in the effective and efficient in school governance. A letter of request for utilizing this tool was sent to the author asking permission to utilize the research instrument. The tool consists of 30 questions answered on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – 5.

Advising. The Advising competency area includes the knowledge, skills and attitudes related to developing a high level of professional standards of quality counseling, coaching, and providing support and direction. This also includes the understanding and application of theories, principles, and concepts of teachers and student development. The leadership competencies mean scores provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of school leaders in the advising domain, encompassing various aspects such as knowledge, skills and attitudes related to development of a high level of professional standards of quality counseling, coaching, and providing support and direction to both teachers and students.

Table 4: Mean rating of the respondent's leadership competency in terms of advising

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I provide counsel or advice to individuals and groups that lead to better self-realization.	4.84	.42	Always
2. I direct individual and groups through processes that hone their skills to deal effectively with personal, educational, and social concerns.	4.84	.42	Always
3. I guide the teachers through developmental programs that will provide life-long learning.	4.88	.33	Always
4. I practice active and effective listening skills.	4.95	.23	Always
5. I provide opportunities for individual teachers to improve their leadership skills and potentials through participation in teacher's activities, organizations, developmental programs and trainings toward their total well-being.	5.00	.00	Always
6. I provide programs that will equip individuals to cope with personal, educational, and social problems through exposure to real life situation.	4.73	.56	Always
7. I open opportunities to integrate with other members of the school community to better understand cultures and diversity.	4.61	.62	Always

8. I develop teachers to become confident, self-directed, effective, and ethical leaders.	4.86	.35	Always
9. I articulate the value of self-leadership and self-management.	4.86	.33	Always
Overall	4.84	.36	Always

The mean percentage scores across different dimensions of advising competency ranges from 4.61 to 5.00, indicating a generally high levels of proficiency among school leaders in these areas. Particularly noteworthy is the highest mean score of 5.00, reflecting the robust provision of opportunities for individual teachers to enhance their leadership skills and overall well-being through participation in developmental programs and activities. The results suggest a strong commitment to fostering professional growth and empowerment among staff members. Furthermore, the mean percentage scores of 4.95 for practicing active listening skills, directing individuals and groups, and developing teachers into confident leaders indicates a solid foundation in communication, guidance, and mentorship. These describe that competencies are crucial in promoting personal and professional development among both teachers and students.

Moreover, the mean percentage score for providing counsel or advice to individuals and groups that lead to better self-realization among school leaders and directing individual and groups through processes that hone their skills to deal effectively with personal, educational, and social concerns presents the same mean percentage score of 4.84. On the other hand, guiding teachers through developmental programs that will provide life-long learning (4.88) and providing programs that will equip individuals to cope with personal, educational, and social problems through exposure to real life situation (4.73). The analysis results indicate that competent school leaders provide relevant training on teacher's professional development which highlight the need for further emphasis on practical, experiential learning opportunities. The results are similar to the study of Kilag and Sasan (2023) which highlights the importance of continuous learning

and professional growth for school leaders, as it enables them to adapt to changing educational contexts and effectively support their staff.

Consequently, it's important to address the areas where the mean percentage scores are slightly lower. For instance, opening opportunities to integrate with the school community to better understand cultures and diversity presents a mean percentage score of 4.61 that suggests a room for improvement in fostering inclusive environments and embracing diverse perspectives. This is supported by the research of Leithwood (2021) which points out the importance of culturally responsive leadership in promoting equitable outcomes and building inclusive school communities. Similarly, research in educational leadership also supports the importance of effective counseling and coaching skills among school leaders (Klar et al., 2019). Effective counseling and coaching are essential components of instructional leadership, enabling school leaders to facilitate teacher growth and enhance instructional practices (Alanoglu, 2021).

Overall, the mean percentage scores of each indicator implies a strong leadership competency in the advising competency. However, it is important to note that there are opportunities for continuous improvement specifically in areas of cultural responsiveness and experiential learning. As cited in the study of Comeaux et al. (2023), school leaders can enhance their effectiveness in providing quality counseling, coaching, and support to promote the holistic development of teachers and students within their schools.

Managing. The Managing competency area includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for the realization of the vision, mission, and core values of the institution. This also includes understanding of the basic principles that underlie conflict in organizations and facilitating the resolution of these conflicts.

Table 5: Mean rating of the respondent's leadership competency in terms of managing

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I show full understanding of the institution's thrust through its vision, mission, and core values.	4.91	.28	Always
2. I exhibit knowledge and understanding of school policy in relation with laws and jurisprudence concerning teachers.	4.93	.25	Always
3. I translate the school's vision-mission into programs and activities that will involve individuals and groups.	4.91	.287	Always
4. I demonstrate ability to implement school policies and programs that are congruent with institutional vision and strategic plans.	4.95	.22	Always
5. I demonstrate basic skills in managing conflict and focusing on resolution, building trust, and establishing rapport.	4.64	.64	Always
6. I demonstrate ability to manage conflicts by leading individuals or groups to a practical, effective, and fair resolution.	4.96	.18	Always
7. I display knowledge in approaching conflict, such as analysis of the issues and interests at stake, cause of the conflict, opportunity of both sides to be heard, and objective resolution of the issue.	4.86	.35	Always

8. I guide towards commitment to a safe, caring, and nurturing environment.	4.80	.40	Always
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Overall	4.87	.33	Always
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The mean scores for leadership competencies in managing provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of school leaders in realizing the vision, mission, and core values of their institutions, as well as managing conflicts and fostering a conducive environment for growth and development. The mean percentage scores ranging from 4.64 to 4.96 in the managing competency suggest a generally high level of proficiency among school leaders in managing various aspects of their roles. The indicator of showing full understanding of the institution's thrust through its vision, mission, and core values (4.91) suggests that school leaders often possess a comprehensive comprehension of the institution's guiding principles, exhibiting knowledge and understanding of school policy in relation with laws and jurisprudence concerning teacher's competency (4.93) indicates that school leaders often demonstrate a robust understanding of school policies and their alignment with legal requirements. This analysis is interpreted as a crucial competency for ensuring compliance and creating a legally sound educational environment.

Moreover, translating the school's vision-mission into programs and activities that will involve individuals and groups mean percentage score of 4.91 which interpreted as "often" suggests that school leaders are effective in translating the institution's vision and mission into actionable plans that engage stakeholders. This leadership competency is essential for ensuring the implementation of strategic initiatives across the organization. On the other hand, demonstrating the ability to implement school policies and programs that are congruent with institutional vision and strategic plans competency (4.95) results indicates that school leaders often exhibit a high level of proficiency in implementing policies and programs aligned with the institution's vision and strategic plans. Meanwhile, demonstrating basic skills in managing conflict and focusing on resolution, building trust, and establishing rapport with the mean percentage score of 4.64 proposed school leaders possess basic skills in conflict management, though there is more variability in this area.

Additionally, demonstrating ability to manage conflicts (4.96) and displaying knowledge in approaching conflict (4.86) indicators suggest that school leaders often possess the knowledge required to approach conflicts effectively, including analyzing issues, understanding interests, and facilitating objective resolutions. School leaders often demonstrate a high level of proficiency in managing conflicts by effectively leading individuals or groups towards resolution. Likewise, the indicator of guiding towards commitment to a safe, caring, and nurturing environment with a mean percentage score of 4.80 indicates that school leaders guide their teams towards a commitment to creating a safe, caring, and nurturing environment.

The findings of the study indicate a strong emphasis on the role of leadership in creating supportive environments that facilitate student learning and development as cited in the study of Darling-Hammond and Cook-Harvey (2018). Danilwan and Dirhamsyah (2022) study also underscores the importance of conflict management skills in promoting positive school climates and enhancing organizational effectiveness. Likewise, Shi and Xie (2023) underscore the critical role of leaders' understanding of the vision and mission in promoting organizational effectiveness and achieving desired outcomes. School leaders must be knowledgeable in leadership policies and its impact on school performance (Kilag & Sasan, 2023), aligning leadership actions with organizational goals to improve school outcomes (Day et al., 2020), and the importance of strategic leadership (Samimi et al., 2022).

Leading. The Leading competency area includes the knowledge, skills and abilities required of a leader to work effectively, to envision, to plan, to effect change, and to address issues in and out of the organization. This also includes subordination of personal agenda, and observance of ethical practice at work. The mean scores provided for leadership competencies in leading offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of school leaders in various aspects of leading their organizations. These competencies encompass the ability to work effectively, envision, plan, effect change, and address issues within and outside the organization.

Table 6: Mean rating of the respondent's leadership competency in terms of leading

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I manifest subordination of personal needs and wants to the higher objectives and principles.	4.79	.49	Always
2. I articulate principles and essence of teamwork that focus on organizational success rather than on personal interest.	4.93	.26	Always
3. I develop partnerships and alliances despite differences and diverse values and principles.	4.93	.26	Always
4. I respond to the needs of teachers and employees over and above self-interest.	4.77	.54	Always
5. I display a strong foundation of values and qualities of a resonant leader.	4.84	.42	Always
6. I exhibit the ability to devote time and energy to leading the process of enabling others to clarify their personal core values that will serve as the basis of their decision-making.	4.91	.29	Always
7. I exhibit the ability to show awareness of one's limitations by recognizing the need for the supervision and guidance of others.	4.89	.31	Always
Overall	4.87	.37	Always

It may be deemed in Table 4 that the respondents got a high level of proficiency in leading their organization as evidenced by 4.87 mean percentage score. This was displayed by demonstrate a strong commitment to prioritizing organizational objectives

over personal interests, as evidenced by high mean percentage score for manifesting subordination of personal needs (4.79) and responding to the needs of teachers and employees (4.77), articulating principles of teamwork (4.93) and developing partnerships despite differences in values (4.93) suggest that school leaders excel in fostering collaborative environments that promote organizational success.

Moreover, developing partnerships and alliances despite differences and diverse values and principles (4.93) indicates that school leaders often excel in developing partnerships and alliances despite differences in values and principles, responding to the needs of teachers and employees over and above self-interest (4.77), displaying a strong foundation of values and qualities of a resonant leader competency (4.84), exhibiting the ability to devote time and energy to leading the process of enabling others to clarify their personal core values that will serve as the basis of their decision-making (4.91), and exhibiting the ability to show awareness of one's limitations by recognizing the need for the supervision and guidance of others (4.89).

These competencies are essential for effective leadership as it fosters a focus on the collective goals of the institution. Effective teamwork is crucial for achieving organizational goals and fostering a collaborative work environment. As cited in the study of Zaidi and Siddiqui (2021), self-sacrifice, putting organizational goals above personal interests in effective leadership, and promoting teamwork and collaboration for organizational effectiveness. Leaders' humility in building trust is important in demonstrating collaborative relationships within organizations (Soderberg and Romney, 2022), and creating positive work environments and driving organizational success (Ramaswamy et al., 2022). The result also supports the study of Gultekin and Dougherty (2021) which gives importance on being a servant leader in educational settings where leaders prioritize the needs of their followers and the organization above their own.

Relating. The Relating competency area includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to interact with individuals and groups with diverse views. This also includes the needed communication competence of student affairs and services practitioners. The provided data offers insights into the leadership competencies of school leaders in relating,

which encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to interact effectively with individuals and groups with diverse views.

Table 7: Mean rating of the respondent's leadership competency in terms of relating

	Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1.	I demonstrate responsibility, accountability, maturity, and consistent propensity for transparency that leads to the development of trusting relationships.	4.64	.67	Always
2.	I show understanding of the requirements for social cohesion, such as respect for and appreciation of values, beliefs, identity, biases, heritage, cultures, and histories of others that create an inclusive environment.	4.90	.31	Always
3.	I manifest self-awareness, empathy, and effective interpretation of underlying emotional and motivational states of others.	4.64	.67	Always
4.	I help others to transform through role-modeling.	4.95	.22	Always
5.	I show basic knowledge of human behavior and human psychology that is useful to identify ways to address students concerns.	4.77	.50	Always
6.	I show sensitivity to others' feelings.	4.73	.49	Always

7.	I demonstrate skills to use written, spoken, and non-verbal languages, efficiently and effectively.	4.86	.35	Always
8.	I demonstrate willingness to communicate with people in their level that result in effective information exchange.	4.80	.40	Always
9.	I provide an avenue for a healthy dialogue with students, parents, and other concerned individuals in or out of the organization.	4.70	.57	Always
10.	I exhibit effective listening skill that leads to a better understanding of complex ideas and situations.	4.89	.31	Always
Overall		4.79	.45	Always
<p>A closer look on Table 7 generally indicates a high level of proficiency among school leaders in various aspects of relating, with several competencies showing particularly strong performance as evidenced by 4.79 mean percentage. The mean percentage score for demonstrating responsibility, accountability, maturity, and consistent propensity for transparency that leads to the development of trusting relationships competency (4.64), showing understanding of the requirements for social cohesion, such as respect for and appreciation of values, beliefs, identity, biases, heritage, cultures, and histories of others that create an inclusive environment competency (4.90), manifesting self-awareness, empathy, and effective interpretation of underlying emotional and motivational (4.64), helping others to transform through role-modeling (4.95), showing basic knowledge of human behavior and human psychology that is useful to identify ways to address students concerns (4.77),and showing sensitivity to others' feelings (4.73).</p> <p>Moreover, demonstrating skills to use written, spoken, and non-verbal languages, efficiently and effectively competency (4.86), demonstrating willingness to communicate</p>				

with people in their level that result in effective information exchange competency (4.80), resulting in an exchange of information, providing an avenue for a healthy dialogue with students, parents, and other concerned individuals in or out of the organization competency (4.70), and exhibiting effective listening skill that leads to a better understanding of complex ideas and situations (4.89).

The findings indicated that school leaders often provide avenues for healthy dialogue with stakeholders, both within and outside the organization. As cited in the study of Shore and Chung (2021), leaders' awareness of social identity and biases in fostering inclusive environments is important. Communication skills (Syakur et al., 2020), trust, empathy (Islam et al., 2021), dialogue (Edwards-Groves et al., 2020), and authentic leadership (Mousa et al., 2019) positively influence the success of the organization, the well-being of the employees, and driving organizational change. Zivkovic (2022) cited as well in his study the importance of empathetic listening in leadership and its impact on building strong relationships and fostering innovation.

Level of Resilience of School Leaders

The study of Langford et al. (2014) highlighted the significance of resilience in fostering positive school climates and student outcomes. They argued that resilient leaders create supportive environments where both staff and students feel empowered to overcome challenges and achieve success. The high mean resilience score could indicate the presence of such conducive environments within the schools represented in your data. In assessing the level of resiliency of the respondents, the researcher utilized the Connor Davidson Resilience Scale (CD RISC) for data gathering in the quantitative phase of this study. This instrument measures resilience or how well a person is equipped to bounce back after a stressful event, tragedy, or trauma.

Table 8. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to adapt to change

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I am able to adapt when changes occur.	3.59	.50	True Nearly All the Time
2. I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships.	3.61	.59	True Nearly All the Time
3. I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles.	3.98	.13	True Nearly All the Time
4. I have a strong sense of purpose in life.	3.89	.31	True Nearly All the Time
5. I feel in control of my life.	3.66	.48	True Nearly All the Time
Overall	3.75	.40	True Nearly All the Time

It can be deemed in the table 8 that a high level of resilience among respondents, as evidenced by a mean percentage score of 3.75 (True Nearly All the Time). The data reveals a high adaptability to change (3.59), a strong ability to recover from adversity (3.61), belief in achieving goals despite obstacles (3.98), a strong sense of purpose (3.89), and a sense of control over their lives (3.66). These findings indicate that respondents generally view themselves as extremely resilient, which is consistent with current research on resilience. According to studies, those with high resilience scores tend to have higher mental health and well-being. Study of Bonano (2021) emphasize that resilience is a common reaction to adversity, with most people demonstrating resilience in a variety of hard situations.

Table 9. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to deal with what comes along the way

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. When there are no clear solutions to my problems, sometimes fate or God can help.	3.68	.51	True Nearly All the Time
2. I can deal with whatever comes my way.	3.54	.66	True Nearly All the Time
3. Good or bad, I believe that most things happen for a reason.	3.66	.55	True Nearly All the Time
4. In dealing with life's problems, sometimes you have to act on a hunch without knowing why.	3.77	.47	True Nearly All the Time
5. I work to attain my goals no matter what roadblocks I encounter along the way.	3.61	.49	True Nearly All the Time
Overall	3.66	.54	True Nearly All the Time

The data reveals that respondents' resilience on their ability to deal with challenges and adaptive coping strategies suggests a high level of confidence as evidence by a mean percentage score of 3.66 (True Nearly All the Time), indicating that respondents frequently rely on various mechanisms to manage life's difficulties. The belief that fate or God can help when there are no clear solutions to problem (3.68), dealing with whatever comes my way (3.54), believing that most things happen for a reason whether it is good or bad (3.66), sometimes acting on a hunch without knowing why in dealing with life's problems (3.77), and working to attain my goals no matter what roadblocks encounter along the way (3.61). These findings revealed that the respondents are strong and capable

when facing life's challenges. Respondents scoring high demonstrate a high level of optimism and self-efficacy, traits closely associated with resilience (Bingöl, 2019).

Table 10. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to cope up with stress

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I have at least one close and secure relationship that helps me when I am stressed.	3.68	.61	True Nearly All the Time
2. Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.	3.54	.66	True Nearly All the Time
3. During times of stress/crisis, I know where to turn for help.	3.66	.48	True Nearly All the Time
Overall	3.63	.58	True Nearly All the Time

It can be deemed in the table 10 that respondents' resilience in terms of managing stress reveals a strong perception of social support, good stress coping techniques, and resourcefulness. The ability to cope up with stress (3.63) indicates that respondents generally feel well-supported and capable of handling stress. Having at least one close and secure relationship that helps them when they're stressed (3.68) emphasize the important role of social support and stress management. Research supports this finding that strong social connections are crucial for resilience. Southwick and Charney (2018), for instance, emphasize the importance of social support networks in providing emotional sustenance and practical assistance, both of which are necessary for stress management and resilience building.

On the other hand, having to cope with stress can make me stronger (3.54) indicates that respondents see stress as a chance for personal growth and development., Knowing where to turn for help during times of stress/crisis (3.66) has a well-developed

sense of resourcefulness and the ability to seek help when necessary. The results suggest that respondents generally feel supported by close relationships, regard stress as a possible source of strength, and know where to go for aid during stressful situations. However, it's important to acknowledge potential limitations and contradictions in the findings. While the mean resilience score suggests overall high resilience among school leaders, individual variation and contextual factors may influence this interpretation. For instance, studies of Ding et al. (2023) have identified challenges such as burnout, stress, and lack of support that can undermine resilience among educational leaders. These factors may not be fully captured by the mean resilience score alone and could warrant further investigation.

Table 11. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to stay focused and think clearly

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I give my best effort no matter what the outcome may be.	3.71	.46	True Nearly All the Time
2. Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly.	3.80	.40	True Nearly All the Time
3. I prefer to take the lead in solving problems rather than letting others make all the decisions.	3.71	.46	True Nearly All the Time
4. I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties.	3.73	.45	True Nearly All the Time
Overall	3.74	.44	True Nearly All the Time

It can be deemed in the table 11 that respondents' resilience in terms of their ability to stay focused and think clearly suggests an excellent competence and efficacy in dealing with stressful situations with a mean percentage score of 3.74 (true nearly all the time).

Giving the best effort no matter what the outcome may be (3.71) demonstrating a great dedication to work and perseverance. The high mean rating for staying focus and think clearly under pressure (3.80) suggest that respondents feel capable of maintaining clarity and concentration under pressure. This ability is an important component of cognitive resilience, which includes preserving cognitive function while under stress. The preference for taking the lead in solving problems (3.71) suggests a proactive and leadership-oriented approach to situations. The study of Hannah et al. (2020) confirms that persons who take the initiative and exhibit leadership traits tend to be more resilient. This proactive approach enables them to successfully impact results and handle hurdles. Thinking of oneself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties (3.74) emphasizes a strong self-concept and self-efficacy in handling hardship.

Table 12. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to not get discouraged in the face of failure

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Past successes give me confidence in dealing with new challenges and difficulties.	3.43	.83	True Nearly All the Time
2. I am not easily discouraged by failure.	3.84	.37	True Nearly All the Time
3. I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people, if it is necessary.	3.66	.58	True Nearly All the Time
4. I like challenges.	3.88	.33	True Nearly All the Time
5. I take pride in my achievements.	3.88	.33	True Nearly All the Time
Overall	3.74	.49	True Nearly All the Time

It can be deemed in the table 12 that respondents' resilience in the face of failure reveals a strong level of self-confidence, persistence, and a positive attitude toward difficulties and accomplishments. The mean percentage score (3.74) indicates a strong resilience profile among the respondents. The past successes give me confidence in dealing with new challenges and difficulties (3.43) highlights the role of previous achievements in fostering confidence for future challenges. Not easily discouraged by failure (3.84) indicates a strong resistance to setbacks and a tendency to persist despite failures. Making unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people (3.66) reflects a willingness to take responsibility and make tough decisions. Liking challenges and taking pride in their achievement (3.88) indicate a positive attitude towards challenges and a strong sense of accomplishment. The study of Hannah et al. (2020), suggests that leadership characteristics, such as the ability to make difficult decisions, are associated with increased resilience. Leaders frequently face difficult situations that require decisive action, and their ability to overcome these obstacles contributes to their resilience. Furthermore, resilient individuals perceive failure as a learning opportunity rather than a setback, allowing them to bounce back and continue pursuing their goals (Stoverink et al., 2020).

Table 13. Mean rating of the respondent's resilience in terms of the ability to handle unpleasant feelings such as anger, pain or sadness

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems.	3.52	.69	True Nearly All the Time
2. Even when things look hopeless, I don't give up.	3.79	.41	True Nearly All the Time
3. I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger.	3.66	.48	True Nearly All the Time

Overall	3.66	.53	True Nearly All the Time
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It can be deemed in the table 14 that respondents' resilience in dealing with negative sensations such as anger, discomfort, or sadness (3.66) show that they have strong emotional regulation and adaptive coping techniques. Trying to see the humorous side of things when facing with problems (3.52) highlights the use of humor as a coping mechanism. Not giving up even when things look hopeless (3.79) indicates strong persistence and determination in the face of hardship. Lastly, being able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger (3.66) reflect a high level of emotional management. Emotional regulation is essential for resilience because it allows people to manage their emotional responses to stress and adversity successfully. The study of Polizzi and Lynn (2021) emphasizes that the ability to regulate emotions is important to psychological resilience. Regulating emotions can help individuals to maintain emotional balance and cope up with stress more effectively.

Primary Challenges Identified by School Leaders

This part analyzes interview findings and presents relevant data aligned with the study’s goals. The chosen methodology facilitated data collection to deepen understanding of the research topic. To aid reflection, interview guides were sent to the participants beforehand.

Guide Question: As a school administrator, what are the primary challenges you have encountered that requires you to be resilient?

Participant 1.

“The COVID-19 pandemic presented our school with unprecedented challenge. It challenges our resilience, adaptability, and governance. As a school administrator, I was responsible in guiding my school through that uncertain period. I needed to ensure that we to provide quality education while protecting the health and wellbeing of my teachers, students, and other stakeholders.”

When P1 was asked about the transition of learning, he mentioned that “the transition to remote learning was perhaps the most difficult. He had to make sure that students and teachers were equipped with the necessary technologies or gadgets to facilitate remote learning. As the gradual in-person classes began, we implemented strict protocols, including regular sanitation of classrooms, social distancing, health monitoring, and procure safety gears to prevent the spread of the virus. This has also contributed to the increase of operational budget allotted to our school.”

He added that he also recognized the mental impact of the pandemic. “Throughout the pandemic, we established continuous wellness program and stress management workshops. The surveys and virtual meetings provided us valuable information into what was working and what are the things needed to improve.” He concluded that “managing the COVID-19 pandemic was an extraordinary test of my resilience as a school leader. It tests my effectiveness as an administrator in managing school and its organization.”

Participant 2.

“As a school administrator, one of the recent and difficult challenges I faced was handling the return of in-person learning during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. This transition on learning modality required careful planning, coordination, and adaptation to ensure the safety of students and teachers.” She also emphasized that the transition requires health and safety protocols, addressing concerns, and maintain effective governance in the face of uncertainty. “Maintaining the resilience of organizational performance and governance during this time period involved strategic decision-making, clear communication, and a dedication to meeting the needs of our school community.”

Participant 3.

“One difficult period for our school happened during a budget crisis. This was due to increased operational costs. As a school administrator, I was faced with enormous responsibility of preserving our school’s operation amidst financial constraints.”

“This situation required immediate action to prevent learning disruptions. It was a pressing challenge to develop a financial strategy that would allow us to operate within

the budget allocated while minimizing its impact on educational quality.” Her adjustment to this challenge was “maintaining the quality of education amidst budget cuts but it requires to streamline operations by consolidating administrative functions and optimizing the use of resources.”

Participant 3 added, “Throughout this crisis, we focused on continuous improvement and adaptations by encouraging innovative solutions to maximize our resources.”

Participant 4.

“About five years ago, I experienced a major challenge in my career as a school administrator when a severe storm caused extensive damage to several classrooms including the principal’s office and the library. Our school is located in the bay area and the damage was so severe that it rendered these facilities unusable for a period. After the storm, I immediately convened an emergency meeting with key administrators and the barangay emergency services to identify how severe the damage was and to come up with a recovery plan.”

“My top priority is to ensure the safety of my student and teachers” he said, “so I decided to close the school temporarily while conducting a thorough inspection of the buildings.” “With several classrooms damaged, we created a temporary solution for learning continuity. We implemented a staggered schedule where different grade levels attended classes at different time of a day.” Facilities were not only the problem he faced, as well as the substantial resources for repairs and reconstruction. “We launched a fundraising campaign including outreach to alumni, local government unit, businesses, and community members. We also reallocated existing funds to prioritize emergency repairs and other essential services.”

Long-term recovery and improvement were also mentioned by participant 4. “We created a crisis management committee and develop a comprehensive long-term recovery plan. The said plan focusses on rebuilding and improving our facilities, upgrading it to be more resilient against future natural disasters and incorporating educational technologies.”

Participant 5.

“Our school faced a public relation crisis a few years ago. The problem arose from charges of misconduct against a teacher which drew extensive media attention and threatened the reputation and integrity of the school and the bureaucracy. When the issue surfaced, we were faced with the urgent need to address the issue to minimize its impact on our school.” She said that “maintaining our organizational values is essential in handling this kind of crisis while maintaining the trust and confidence of our school.”

In response to the crisis, she developed a crisis management team to direct their response efforts, developed communication strategies, and ensured transparency, accountability, and due process. “We emphasized an open and honest communication with all stakeholders, including parents, students, teachers, and the general public. We offered updates on the situation, addressed the claims, reiterated our commitment to transparency, integrity, and accountability. Moreover, we still adhered to strict due process in handling allegations, ensuring fairness, impartiality, and respect the rights of the involved individuals.” She added that, “Our focus shifted towards rebuilding trust after the issue subsided. We restored the reputation of the school and strengthened the governance structure to prevent similar incidents in the future.”

“That crisis challenged our school’s reputation which emphasized the importance of crisis management, ethical leadership, and preserving the integrity of the school.”

Participant 6.

Participant 6 shared that “When my school received a bomb threat, it was an extraordinary challenging situation. This unusual incident disrupted our school operation, putting our students and teachers at risk. That incident sent tremors throughout our school community. Parents, students, and teachers were anxious, instilling uncertainty.”

“In response, we immediately implemented our emergency procedures and came up with a strategic action plan to address the threat. The security and safety of my students and teachers were my concern.” She added that “law enforcement, bomb squad, and Philippine National Police investigated and searched the entire school. Incident debriefing sessions for students, teachers, and non-teaching employees were conducted to process

the experience and reactions to the bomb threat. These provide a safe space for them to share their thoughts and feelings.”

She also quoted an important lesson. “The bomb threat crisis served for me, as a school leader, a valuable learning experience that I need to improve our emergency preparedness and response protocols. It tested my crisis management, decisive leadership, and resilience. After which, I implemented training programs on bomb threat protocols and conducted emergency drills to prepare our teachers for future security threats.”

Participant 7.

“COVID-19 was one of the most recent challenging periods I faced most especially the transition to hybrid learning amidst the pandemic. The transition required us to balance the health and safety of our students and teachers to provide quality education and maintain effective governance. It challenged our school community to adapt the new teaching modalities, implement innovative educational technologies, and ensure access to education for all students in our school.”

“The transition to other learning modalities had a significant impact to our school, affecting our administrative operation. We procured additional devices such as laptops, and upgraded our internet connection to ensure that all teachers can deliver their lessons through remote learning.” He added that they conducted professional development workshops and training sessions for teachers. “Teachers need to familiarize themselves with online learning platforms, online teaching, and other practices for online learning.”

Participant 8.

“As a school administrator, I was coping with crisis emerged to a series of safety incidents within our school including threats of violence, bullying, and student conflicts. Maintaining safe organization required a comprehensive approach to address safety concerns, enhancing security measures, and fostering a culture of safety and well-being for all members of our school.”

“In response, we improved our security measures and increase our surveillance, access to control measures, and the presence of security personnel in our schools.” She

further shared that “prevention and intervention strategies were important in addressing the root causes of safety incidents and promoting a positive and supportive school climate.”

Participant 9.

“As a school administrator, one of the most difficult times I faced was dealing with teacher shortage that threatened our instructional continuity. Teacher shortage situation has immediate consequences for our school affecting classroom instruction. Managing classes with just a handful of teachers presented challenges which requires us to be innovative to ensure quality education and effective instruction. We implemented strategies to reduce class size such as combining smaller classes.”

Participant 10.

“Several years ago, our school was hit by a severe flooding incident. Floodwaters filled our school premises inflicting a major facility damage which disrupt the school operation. The flood posed a significant risk to the safety and well-being of students, teachers, and staff. As a school administrator, I was thrown into a crisis management role, but I was resilient despite of the devastating flood.”

“I activated our emergency response plan, mobilizing emergency response team. I implemented evacuation protocols to ensure everyone safety. Stakeholders near our school were safely evacuated from flood-affected areas to designated evacuation sites.” She further shared that “effective communication was very important in this type of emergency, providing timely updates and keeping my stakeholders informed about the situation and response efforts. We conducted a thorough assessment of the damage caused by the flooding and develop a recovery plan to restore our normal school operation.”

“The flooding presented unprecedented challenges for our school, but through strategic planning and collaborative efforts, we were able to navigate through the crisis. We remain committed in enhancing our emergency preparedness, improving our school infrastructure, and fostering a culture of resilience to ensure the safety of our school community.”

Discussion

In an unforeseen situation such as excessive rain, risk of storm, earthquakes, and extreme temperatures in the region, administrators try to prepare emergency action plans and prepare for possible alternatives to make schools ready (Sari & Nayır, 2020). Education scholars believe that high education institutions and organizations can influence and define school principal's leadership practices (Wieczorek & Manard, 2018). Principals are expected to continuously execute change and school improvement projects and to prepare students for the 21st century (Mahfouz, 2018). They are also required to attend the demands of the school by sustaining positive interpersonal relationships and solving conflicts that may arise (Maxwell & Riley, 2017). School administrators are expected to be leaders with heavy accountability to lead reform efforts for the school improvement.

In the given narrative, three Participants cited the COVID-19 was one of the challenges they have faced as a school administrator. The COVID-19 pandemic has prompted the closure of many physical activities which leads to educational institution to migrate to distance learning and has posed substantial challenges for educational activities worldwide (Heng & Sol, 2021). It is undeniable that the recent pandemic test the resilience, adaptability, and strategic responses of school administrators. These participants narrated the impact of the pandemic. It underscores the profound challenges and strategic response involved in managing the impact of the pandemic in the educational institutions. Czerniewicz et al. (2019) study reveals that teachers felt prepared to teach online since they are already using online technologies. The transition to remote and distance learning ensured the learning continuity. The studies of Mackey (2012) and Tull et al. (2020) describes that in the event of an earthquake, education institutions had to re-establish communication with students and move the learning into online. The pandemic significantly changes the performance of numerous organizations, organizations need to be resilient to be flexible and sensitive to a variety of changing circumstances (Pandita et al., 2023). In Coquyt (2021) study, for superintendents to improve their flexibility and adaptability in decision-making and to improve their communication with all interested parties by being more transparent and routinely seeking stakeholder feedback,

superintendents can hone their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The capacity for critical decision-making in the face of uncertainty, self-control, and communication responses to the redesigned framework for leadership competencies (Camiel et al., 2022).

On the other hand, participants also narrated the budget crisis and teacher shortage was one of their enormous responsibilities of preserving her school's operation. Financial is a critical responsibility in education administration. This narrative explores the lived experience of a school administrator who shouldered a task of navigating her school budget crisis in preserving school operation. The participant's financial instability problem threatened not only the academic programs but also the survival of the school she governed. Shortage of teachers also presents a threat to the learning continuity of teachers. Despite the challenges, the participant combined cost-cutting, revenues generation through income generating projects, and asking for community support. The experience in the narrative strengthened community engagement in educational administration. Du Plessis and Mestry (2019) also cited in their study that rural schools face severe challenges that unique to their environment such as insufficient funding from the state, insufficient teaching force, and lack of resources are barriers to effective education. The same study emphasize that policy makers need to put strategies to improve the working conditions to improve learning achievement.

Moreover, Natural disasters pose significant challenges to educational institutions, often resulting in extensive damage that disrupts school operation and poses safety risks. This delves in to the experiences of two participant where a severe storm caused an extensive damage to his school. This participant describes that high winds, heavy rainfall, and flooding destroyed the school buildings and infrastructure. Despite of the circumstances, both school leaders ensured everyone's safety, provided safety measures, and provided emergency services. The experience underscored the importance of being prepared and resilient in planning and managing natural disaster events. They have a critical role of effective leadership, comprehensive planning, and community involvement in overcoming the aftermath of a natural disasters. It emphasizes the importance of being resilient and prepared to preserve learning continuity. As cited by Ng, et al., (2020), leadership has a significant effect on community resilience. School leaders should

recognize the impending crisis warning signs and organize their responsive strategy (Alarcon, 2021).

Managing a teacher misconduct and preserving the school integrity is a crisis that a participant narrated in the study. An allegation of misconduct against a teacher can profoundly impact the reputation of an educational institution. The allegation did not only threaten the teacher’s career but also risked the school’s reputation. The participant further narrated that the said incident provided clarity and accountability which leads to appropriate legal and disciplinary actions. On the other hand, threats of violence in schools also presents a serious safety and well-being of students and teachers. Strategic measures were implemented ensuring the safety of all individuals during a safety incident, threats of violence, student conflicts and bomb threat. Collaboration with the law enforcement was effective in managing immediate threat which highlights that critical role of crisis management strategies in protecting the well-being of teachers and students. These incidents improved the resilience of educational institutions in the face of similar threats. Studies of Moerschell and Novak (2019) explores the challenges of university leadership in planning and aligning communications and activities before, during, and after crises. The study examined the unpredictable natural or man-made crises that can threaten people which emphasized the urgent need for attention and action. Similarly, Goodrum et al. (2018) study on threat assessment management suggests the need to examine the threat assessment trainings, forms, and procedures, as well as parent’s and student’s perceptions among school organizations.

Common themes and findings found in the convergence of data presented

Table 14: Common Findings and Themes found in the Convergence of Data Presented

Findings	Themes
<p>Leadership Competencies (Advising) I provide opportunities for individual teachers to improve their leadership skills and potentials through participation in</p>	<p>Teacher empowerment</p>

<p>teacher’s activities, organizations, developmental programs, and trainings toward their total well-being. (5.00 - Always descriptive rating)</p> <p>I provide programs that will equip individuals to cope with personal, educational, and social problems through exposure to real life situation. (4.73 – Often Descriptive Rating)</p>	
<p>Leadership Competencies (Managing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I demonstrate ability to implement school policies and programs that are congruent with institutional vision and strategic plans. (4.95 - Often Descriptive Rating) • I demonstrate ability to manage conflicts by leading individuals or groups to a practical, effective, and fair resolution. (4.96 - Often Descriptive Rating) • I display knowledge in approaching conflict, such as analysis of the issues and interests at stake, cause of the conflict, opportunity of both sides to be heard, and objective resolution of the issue. (4.86 - Often Descriptive Rating) 	<p>Decision-making</p>
<p>Leadership Competencies (Advising)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I articulate principles and essence of teamwork that focus on 	<p>Communication</p>

organizational success rather than on personal interest. (4.93 - Often Descriptive Rating)

- I develop partnerships and alliances despite differences and diverse values and principles. (4.93 - Often Descriptive Rating)
- I exhibit the ability to show awareness of one's limitations by recognizing the need for the supervision and guidance of others. (4.89- Often Descriptive Rating)

Leadership Competencies (Relating)

- I show understanding of the requirements for social cohesion, such as respect for and appreciation of values, beliefs, identity, biases, heritage, cultures, and histories of others that create an inclusive environment. (4.90 - Often Descriptive Rating)
- I demonstrate willingness to communicate with people in their level that result in effective information exchange. (4.80 - Often Descriptive Rating)
- I exhibit effective listening skill that leads to a better understanding of complex ideas and situations. (8.89 - Often Descriptive Rating)

Level Resilience of School	Resilience
<p>Administrators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles. (3.89 – Nearly all the time descriptive rating)• Even when things look hopeless, I don't give up. (3.79 – Nearly all the time descriptive rating)• Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly. (3.80 - Nearly all the time descriptive rating)• I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger. (3.66 - Nearly all the time descriptive rating)• I work to attain my goals no matter what roadblocks I encounter along the way. (3.61 - Nearly all the time descriptive rating)	

Effects of Leadership Competencies in the Resilience in Organizational Performance and Governance

In the study, the hypothesis states that school administrators' competencies do not significantly affect resilience in organizational performance and governance. The data collected were subjected to regression analysis to determine the extent of impact of the predictor variables cause on the criterion variable.

Table 15: Multiple Regression Analysis between Leadership Qualities and Resilience in Organizational Performance and Governance

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	3.220	1.008		3.193	.852
Advising	.111	.120	.130	.927	.358
Managing	.054	.125	.061	.435	.665
Leading	-.060	.095	-.088	-.627	.534
Relating	-.007	.096	-.011	-.078	.938
		r-squared = .027			
		r-value = .027			
		f-value = .360			
		p-value = .852			
		alpha = .05			

Results of the regression analysis indicate that the 4 variables of leadership competencies of school leaders do not significantly affect the resilience in organizational performance and governance to a different extent as shown by the .852 coefficients. The table of coefficients shows that the B coefficient represents change in the dependent variable for a one-unit change in the independent variable. Advising increases one-unit in the independent variable corresponds to a .111 unit increase in the dependent variable. The B coefficient of Advising (.111) suggests that it has a positive effect on the outcome. Similarly, Managing B coefficient .054 implies a positive effect of managing on the outcome. However, Leading (-.060) and Relating (-.007) B-coefficients suggest a negative effect on the outcome. Looking at the t-statistics and their respective associated p values can conclude that among the four competencies, .358 (advising), .665 (managing), .534 (leading), and .938 (relating) are found to be statistically not significant since is greater than the alpha value of .05.

Analysis of the sustained Beta coefficients would reveal that of four (4) variables of leadership competencies of school leaders, advising, managing, leading, and relating appeared to be the best predictors of resilience in the resilience of organizational

performance and governance. Results of the analysis of variance of the regression of leadership competencies for school leaders revealed an F-value of .360 with a p-value of .852. Since the associated probability exceeds .05 alpha, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Training Program for Sustaining Effective Organizational Performance and School Governance

Skilled workforces can positively impact organizational outcomes (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021). Training develops the thinking and creativity of school leaders for better decision making, complaints handling, and overall effectiveness (Dami et al., 2022). Efforts on training school leaders and teachers' development demonstrate that organizations are capitalizing not only school leaders, but also on teachers who can commit to achieving higher levels of responsibilities. According to Jehanzeb and Mohanty (2018) employee development shows a positive impact on employee job satisfaction and later the job satisfaction has significant impact on organizational commitment, which also has a direct impact on employee's performance (Salas-Vallina et al., 2020). However, such elements need to be envisioned, developed, implemented, and sustained by well-trained individuals. Employee training and development happens at different levels of organization and helps people achieve goals.

Training is one of the probable reasons which can lead to many possible benefits for both the organization and individuals that helps to achieve the objective of the organization (Karim et al., 2019). Training and development are means capture the expectation of human resource criteria and expected performance (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020). Training is defined as the process, or methods of one that acquires the skill, knowledge, and experience. Development of training is a process of using the guideline from the training framework to formulate an instructional strategy that meets the training objectives (Blanchard & Thacker, 2023). There are no doubt that well-trained and developed school administrators will be effective to the organization and will increase the chances of their efficiency in performing their duties and responsibilities. These developmental programs are specific frameworks for helping employees develop their skills, knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and consequently improve their abilities to perform

specific tasks in the workplace (Karim et al., 2019). Figure 3 shows the systematic framework for establishing training programs (Sum, 2007).

Figure 2: A Systematic Framework in Establishing Training Programs

In establishing a training program for sustaining organizational performance and governance, the researcher proposes the followings stages, namely: Training Plan and Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The proposed training plan aims to recommend, implement, and monitor/evaluate the training program to support organizational effectiveness and sustainability in school governance.

Training Plan and Development

Planning a training program for organizational performance and governance begins with assessing the needs of the organization (Kabeyi, 2019). This also follows a training need assessment done through a diagnostic assessment or a review of the needs of the organization. This is to identify the prior knowledge or experience of the school leaders on organizational performance and governance. Training financial cost and other expenditures should be considered such as meeting rooms, meals, refreshment breaks, social functions, accommodation, requirements, equipment, materials, transportation, program schedule, and the training facilitator.

Moreover, plan to use the principles, pedagogical frameworks, methods, skills, metrics, and training processes in creating a training program. The researcher proposes the following steps:

1. Identify the specific topics related to organizational performance and school governance that the organization wants to focus. This includes areas such as leadership, communication, decision-making, policy development, performance management, and collaboration.
2. Understanding the preferences of the school leaders and teachers based on the pre-assessment mentioned earlier.
3. Define the learning goals and outcomes of the training program. Identify what specific skills, knowledge, and attributes should the participants develop or improve. This will serve as a guide for designing the curriculum and assessment methods (Blanchard & Thacker, 2023).

Implementation

Managing a training seminar is vigorous in the success of the whole training program. Coordination activities include meeting rooms, meals, refreshment breaks, social functions, accommodation, requirements, equipment, materials, and the schedule of the training program. These are the proposed steps:

1. Begin with a knowledge-based approach to provide foundational knowledge on organizational performance and school governance (Kansal & Singhal, 2018). This includes explaining the concepts, theories, best practices, and relevant case studies. After which, connect different concepts and topics together. This will help participants to see the interrelations between different aspects of organizational performance and school governance.
2. Use a learning framework to structure the learning experiences. This includes gaining attention, informing participants of the objective, stimulating recall of prior knowledge, presenting the content, providing guidance, producing performance, providing feedback, assessing performance, and enhancing retention and transfer.
3. Incorporate the Socratic Method to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving (Rahman, 2019). Ask open-ended questions to provoke experiences, and engage the participants in discussion, debates and reflections on real-world scenarios or challenges related to the topic. Moreover, apply the 5E's of Instructional Model (Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate) to promote active engagement and hands-on learning (Rodriguez et al., 2019). Encourage participants to actively participate in activities such as group activities, simulations, or role plays to apply their knowledge and skills.
4. Provide contextual learning experiences by using real-life examples and simulations that imitate the challenges and complexities of organizational performance and governance. This will help participants to develop practical skills and understand the relevance of the theories discussed (Dewi & Primayana, 2019). Fostering reflective approach incorporates opportunities for participants to reflect on their learning progress, identify areas for improvement, and set goals for further development.
5. Prioritize collaboration and communication by incorporating activities such as group projects, teamwork exercises, and opportunities for participants to practice effective

communication and collaboration. Motivate the participants through empowerment by incorporating gamification elements such as rewards, challenges, and leaderboards to create a sense of achievement and encourage active participation (Alsawaier, 2018).

6. Finally, ensure that the training program is culturally responsive and inclusive through incorporating diverse perspectives, respecting different cultural backgrounds, and promoting equity and fairness in the learning environment (Bottiani et al., 2017).

Evaluation

Participants’ evaluation should be always conducted at the end of the training sessions. Evaluation provides valuable feedback that helps to evaluate the program. Using learning metrics such as knowledge acquisition, skill development, participants engagement, knowledge retention and recall, critical thinking and problem-solving, collaboration and communication, self-reflection and metacognition, feedback and improvement, motivation and attitudes, and training learning outcomes and goals achievement. Participants comment and suggestions will also be used to improve future training programs. Furthermore, this data will provide trainers with information that can be used to establish standard of performance for future training programs (Alsalamah & Callinan, 2021).

Figure 3: Program/Project/Activity (PPA) Proposal

PHASE 1: TRAINING PLAN AND DEVELOPMENT					
OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
a. To set out clear expectation of school heads along well-defined career stages of professional development from beginning to	Total duration: 4 months	36,000Php	Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division	(Months 1-4) • Organizational Needs Assessment • Training Needs Assessment • Financing	Key Findings: 1. Skill Gaps Identified: • Leadership and Management: Need for advanced training in strategic planning,

<p>exemplary practice; b. Engage school heads to actively embrace a continuing effort to attain high levels of proficiency; and c. Provide support to professional learning and development; and d. Help identify development needs and facilitate uniform assessment of performance .</p>			<p>Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts</p> <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Training Cost</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This Organizational Needs Assessment aims to identify important training requirements for maintaining successful organizational performance and improving school governance. • Methodology: 1. Data Collection: - Surveys and questions distributed to school administrators. - Focus group discussions with key stakeholders. - Individual interviews with 	<p>conflict resolution, and change management.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching and Pedagogy: Enhanced training in modern teaching methodologies, technology integration, and student assessment. • Administrative Efficiency: Improved skills in data management, financial planning, and operational logistics. • Governance: Training in regulatory compliance, policy development, and stakeholder engagement. <p>2. Resource Allocation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient resources
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				<p>leadership and management.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Review of existing performance data and training records. <p>2. Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Quantitative analysis of survey results to identify common skill gaps and training needs.- Qualitative analysis of interview and focus group data to understand contextual challenges and specific requirements.	<p>dedicated to training and development.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need for a dedicated training budget and more accessible training materials.
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OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. To develop training content that directly addresses these gaps;</p> <p>b. Ensure that the training program supports the organization's mission, vision, and strategic objectives;</p> <p>c. Improve efficiency, productivity, and overall effectiveness through targeted training; and</p> <p>d. Equip school administrators with the necessary skills and knowledge for effective governance.</p>	<p>Total duration: 4 months</p>	<p>36,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>(Months 5-8)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Program Construction and Development • The goal of designing and developing a training program to sustain successful organizational performance and improve school governance is to produce a systematic, meaningful, and long-term approach to staff development. This effort aims to address current skill gaps, promote best practices, 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhanced efficiency and productivity due to better-trained staff. 2. Increased alignment with strategic goals leading to better execution of initiatives. 3. Increased stakeholder confidence through transparent and ethical governance. 4. Promotion of a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

				<p>and match training with the organization's and educational institution's strategic goals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Methodology <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Develop a curriculum that addresses identified needs and aligns with strategic goals.2. Incorporate diverse training methods, including workshops, seminars, e-learning, and hands-on activities.3. Roll out the training program in phases to ensure smooth integration.4. Provide continuous support and resources to participants throughout the training.	
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PHASE 2: IMPLEMENTATION					
OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Help executives create and implement strategic plans that correspond with organizational goals.</p> <p>b. Provide leaders with tools for successful decision-making and problem-solving.</p> <p>c. Improve leaders' communication skills with stakeholders ; and</p> <p>d. Improve skills in conflict resolution, negotiation, and teamwork.</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>(Month 1-2)</p> <p>Leadership and Management Training</p> <p>Session 1: Seminar on key competencies and skills required for effective organizational performance and governance.</p> <p>Session 2: Strategic Planning and Execution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshops on setting SMART goals, resource allocation, and performance measurement. <p>Session 3: Decision-Making and Problem-Solving</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case studies and simulations to practice problem- 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Effective leaders who create and implement strategic plans for organizational success. 2. Leaders with strong decision-making and problem-solving abilities. 3. Improved results through data-driven initiatives. 4. Improved governance frameworks to promote transparency and accountability. 4. Improved conflict resolution and team-building skills, leading to a collaborative work atmosphere.

				<p>solving in real-world scenarios</p> <p>Session 4: Ethical Leadership and Governance - Workshops on policy development, stakeholder engagement, and accountability</p> <p>Session 5: Training in conflict resolution, negotiation, and team dynamics.</p>	
OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
a. Improve communication skills, including active listening, clear expression, and empathy; b. Encourage knowledge and respect for different opinions	Total duration: 2 months	25,000Php	Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District	(Month 3-4) Session 1: Communication and Collaboration - Seminar on the Importance of Effective Communication, Conflict Resolution, Team building, and networking skills.	1. Improved communication skills for clearer, more effective interactions. 2. Improved staff understanding and respect, leading to fewer disagreements. 3. Improved teamwork and cooperation,

<p>and background s; c. Promote teamwork, cooperation, and knowledge exchange among staff; d. Foster collaboration among departments and stakeholders by bridging gaps; and e. Improve communication tactics for engaging with stakeholders such as parents, students, teachers, and community members.</p>			<p>Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts</p> <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Session 2: Interpersonal Communication Skills: Training on active listening, nonverbal communication, and verbal clarity.</p> <p>Session 3: Collaborative Work Environments - Strategies for effective delegation, decision-making, and problem-solving in teams.</p> <p>Session 4: Conflict Resolution and Negotiation - Techniques for managing conflicts constructively and de-escalating tense situations.</p>	<p>resulting in more productivity and innovation. 4. Improved cooperation and alignment between departments and teams. 5. Improved conflict resolution to create a more favorable work environment. 6. Improved employee morale and satisfaction. 7. Improved stakeholder relationships, leading in stronger support for the educational institution's mission and goals. 8. Enhanced community engagement and relationships.</p>
<p>OBJECTIVES:</p>	<p>COURSES OF ACTION</p>	<p>BUDGET ALLOCATION</p>	<p>RESOURCES</p>	<p>IMPLEMENTATION PLAN</p>	<p>EXPECTED OUTCOME</p>
<p>a. Understand educational</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working</p>	<p>(Month 5-6) Session 1: Educational</p>	<p>1. Improved knowledge of educational</p>

<p>policies and regulations at the local, regional, and national levels; b. Evaluate the impact of policy changes on organizational practices and decision-making; c. Encourage ethical leadership, openness, and accountability among educational leaders and administrators; d. Establish governance frameworks that meet regulatory criteria and build stakeholder trust; and e. Provide leaders with strategies to effectively implement educational initiatives and ensure compliance.</p>			<p>Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Policy and Governance - Seminar on policies, legal frameworks, ethical practices, and their leadership in school governance. Session 2: Educational Policy Analysis - Workshops on analyzing and interpreting educational policies and regulations. Session 3: Ethical Leadership and Governance - Courses on ethical decision-making, integrity, and professional conduct. Session 4: Policy Implementation and Compliance - Strategies for developing</p>	<p>policies and procedures among leaders and administrators. 2. Improved ability to negotiate policy complexity and advocate for organizational requirements. 3. Improved effectiveness in implementing educational policies and regulations. 4. Improved compliance and alignment with regulatory standards. 5. Improved stakeholder relationships, resulting in more support for the educational institution's mission and goals.</p>
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OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Improve leaders' capacity to give vision, direction, and support for instructional improvement efforts;</p> <p>b. Provide leaders methods for creating and executing curriculum frameworks that match with educational goals and standards;</p> <p>c. Promote innovative and creative teaching approaches to address students' various needs;</p> <p>d. Provide leaders resources and approaches for</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>policy implementation plans and ensuring compliance.</p> <p>(Month 7-8)</p> <p>Session 1: Instructional Leadership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on instructional supervision, curriculum development, assessment strategies, and data-driven decision-making <p>Session 2: Instructional Leadership Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on vision-setting, goal-setting, and strategic planning for instructional improvement. <p>Session 3: Curriculum Development and Alignment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategies for developing and implementing 	<p>1. Improved educational leaders' ability to drive and support instructional improvement efforts.</p> <p>2. Improved confidence and effectiveness in instructional leadership.</p> <p>3. Improved teaching effectiveness leads to better student learning outcomes.</p> <p>4. Promoted student involvement, motivation, and achievement.</p> <p>5. Improved professional learning communities for better cooperation, sharing best practices, and problem-solving.</p> <p>6. Improved job satisfaction</p>

<p>assessing teaching effectiveness and student progress; and e. Encourage peer learning, sharing best practices, and collaborative problem-solving.</p>				<p>curriculum frameworks that align with standards and educational goals.</p> <p>Session 4: Teaching and Learning Strategies - Training on evidence-based instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, and differentiated instruction.</p>	<p>and professional development opportunities for instructors. 7. Improved alignment between curriculum, instruction, and assessment with educational goals and standards. 8. Improved instructional techniques throughout the educational institution for greater coherence and effectiveness.</p>
OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Develop successful recruitment tactics to attract excellent educators and personnel; b. Implement retention tactics to limit turnover and provide a</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District</p>	<p>(Month 9-10) Session 1: Human Resource Management - skills related training on recruitment, professional development, employee evaluation, and creating a positive work environment. Session 2:</p>	<p>1. Improved ability to attract and retain top talent, resulting in a more stable and competent team. 2. Improved teacher performance and productivity using appropriate performance</p>

<p>stable personnel; c. Provide leaders with tools and approaches to evaluate and improve employee performance ; d. Create professional development plans that correspond with organizational goals; e. Provide leaders on labor laws, regulations, and ethical standards; and f. Develop policies and procedures to ensure compliance and foster a healthy work environment .</p>			<p>Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts</p> <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Recruitment and Retention - Strategies for developing attractive job postings, conducting effective interviews, and selecting the best candidates.</p> <p>Session 3: Performance Management - Methods for addressing performance issues, coaching for improvement, and developing performance improvement plans.</p> <p>Session 4: Professional Development - Planning and implementing professional development programs that align with organizational goals and staff needs.</p>	<p>management approaches. 3. Enhanced employee satisfaction and engagement through ongoing feedback and professional development opportunities. 4. Targeted professional development programs lead to increased workforce skill and knowledge. 5. Improved alignment between staff skills and organizational goals, resulting in better performance and outcomes. 6. Improved understanding of labor rules and regulations to reduce legal risks and compliance problems.</p>
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OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Develop and implement long-term financial plans that match with the school's vision and goals;</p> <p>b. Encourage a culture of financial planning and proactive resource management;</p> <p>c. Provide leaders with tools for effective budgeting and resource allocation;</p> <p>d. Maximize financial resources to promote educational efforts;</p> <p>e. Encourage ethical financial activities and conformity to regulatory norms; and</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>(Month 11-12)</p> <p>Session 1: Financial and Resource Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing knowledge on budgeting, resource allocation, grant management, and financial accountability <p>Session 2: Strategic Financial Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on developing and implementing long-term financial plans that align with school goals. <p>Session 3: Budgeting and Resource Allocation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategies for prioritizing and allocating resources to maximize impact on 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Training for creating and implementing long-term financial plans that correspond with school objectives. 2. Conducted workshops on financial forecasting, risk management, and sustainability methods. 3. Explore budgeting tools and procedures to ensure accuracy and effectiveness. 4. Optimal resource allocation strategies for educational programs. 5. Training for ethical financial practices and regulatory compliance. 6. Conducted workshops on financial reporting, auditing, and accountability systems.

<p>f. Create transparent and accountable financial reporting and auditing processes.</p>				<p>educational programs.</p> <p>Session 4: Financial Accountability and Transparency - Workshops on developing and implementing systems for financial reporting, auditing, and accountability</p>	<p>7. Conducted workshops on fostering trust and teamwork through open financial practices.</p>
<p>OBJECTIVES:</p>	<p>COURSES OF ACTION</p>	<p>BUDGET ALLOCATION</p>	<p>RESOURCES</p>	<p>IMPLEMENTATION PLAN</p>	<p>EXPECTED OUTCOME</p>
<p>a. Train educators to use multiple pedagogical strategies to accommodate different learning styles; b. Encourage the implementation of evidence-based instructional practices to enhance student engagement and accomplishment;</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors</p>	<p>(Month 13-14) Session 1: Pedagogical methods and Delivery - Seminar on utilizing variety of pedagogical methods to engage participants actively through case studies, role-play, group discussions, simulations, and reflective exercise. Session 2:</p>	<p>1. Improved instructional skills resulted in increased student engagement and achievement. 2. Increased use of evidence. 3. Utilizes evidence-based teaching practices and innovative methods. 4. Improve class design and delivery to meet varied learning requirements. 5. Creating positive,</p>

<p>c. Develop techniques for managing diverse classrooms and fostering inclusive learning environment s; d. Encourage the use of student-centered teaching methods that promote active learning and critical thinking; and e. Encourage ongoing professional development through reflective techniques and peer learning.</p>			<p>- Resource person/Field Experts</p> <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Innovative Pedagogical Methods - Training on various teaching methodologies such as project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, flipped classrooms, and differentiated instruction.</p> <p>Session 3: Effective Lesson Delivery - Strategies for using formative and summative assessments to guide instruction and improve student learning.</p> <p>Session 4: Student-Centered Learning - Integration of technology to support personalized learning and student engagement.</p>	<p>inclusive, and well-managed classroom settings that promote learning. 6. Emphasis on student-centered approaches to promote active learning and critical thinking. 7. Improved technology for personalized learning and better student outcomes. 8. Promoted professional development and reflective practice among educators.</p>
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OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Assist school leaders and experienced instructors' mentor and guide their colleagues;</p> <p>b. Provide mentors and coaches with ways to improve teachers' educational techniques;</p> <p>c. Mentor and coach current and future school leaders to strengthen their leadership skills; and</p> <p>d. Foster a healthy school atmosphere that promotes professional development and mutual support.</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>(Month 15-16)</p> <p>Session 1: Mentoring and Coaching</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on instructional supervision, curriculum development, assessment strategies, and data-driven decision-making <p>Session 2: Mentoring and Coaching Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on the foundational principles of effective mentoring and coaching. <p>Session 3: Effective Communication and Feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Techniques for active listening, asking powerful questions, and providing constructive feedback. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop the fundamental principles of effective mentoring and coaching. 2. Conducted workshops on building trust, identifying goals, and generating development plans. 3. Strategies for active listening, asking effective questions, and delivering constructive comments. 4. Strategies for promoting open and honest communication in mentoring and coaching partnerships. 5. Encouraging mentors and coaches to engage in reflective practice to enhance their skills. 6. Encouraging a growth mentality and continual

OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
				Session 4: Reflective Practice and Continuous Improvement - Promoting a growth mindset and continuous improvement among mentees and coaches.	progress among mentees and coaches.
a. Encourage the use of active learning practices to engage students and improve comprehension; b. Create a motivating and engaging learning environment ; c. Promote reflective practice for better understanding and learning; d. Offer continuing professional development	Total duration: 2 months	25,000Php	Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts Resources:	(Month 17-18) Session 1: Experiential Learning - Seminar on apply learning through real-world projects and action plans. Session 2: Activity Design and Implementation - Techniques for designing and implementing experiential learning activities that align with curriculum standards.	1. Improved instructors' capacity to create and implement experiential learning activities. 2. Increased usage of active learning practices in classrooms. 3. Increased student involvement and motivation. 4. Improved learning results by applying classroom principles in real-world settings. 5. Increased focus on reflective practice to enhance

<p>t opportunities for educators; and e. Foster a collaborative environment where instructors share best practices and encourage one another's growth.</p>			<p>Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Session 3: Assessment and Reflection - Methods for incorporating reflective practice to help students and educators evaluate and deepen their learning experiences.</p> <p>Session 4: Collaboration and Professional Development - Continuous professional development sessions to keep educators updated on new experiential learning strategies and tools.</p>	<p>student knowledge. 6. Professional development opportunities for educators. 7. Collaborative school culture promotes continual improvement and sharing of best practices.</p>
<p>OBJECTIVES:</p>	<p>COURSES OF ACTION</p>	<p>BUDGET ALLOCATION</p>	<p>RESOURCES</p>	<p>IMPLEMENTATION PLAN</p>	<p>EXPECTED OUTCOME</p>
<p>a. Improve school leaders' ability to stay focused and successful under pressure;</p>	<p>Total duration: 2 months</p>	<p>25,000Php</p>	<p>Technical Working Committee : - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School</p>	<p>(Month 19-20) Session 1: Resilient Leadership - Seminar on resilient leadership to guide school leaders and</p>	<p>1. Improved leaders' capacity to be successful and composed under pressure. 2. Improved ability to adapt and respond to</p>

<p>b. Encourage leaders to be adaptable and responsive to changing situations; and c. Provide stress management and burnout prevention practices.</p>			<p>Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts</p> <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>principals on different ways to address change in the organization.</p> <p>Session 2: Resilient Leadership Principles - Workshops on adaptive leadership strategies and techniques for navigating change.</p> <p>Session 3: Stress Management and Self-Care - Workshops on self-care practices, including mindfulness, work-life balance, and relaxation techniques.</p> <p>Session 4: Organizational Stability and Growth - Methods for fostering a culture of resilience and continuous improvement within the</p>	<p>obstacles as they arise. 3. Reduced stress and burnout among leaders. 4. Improved the well-being and health of school leaders and administrators. 5. Fostering a culture of resilience and continual development among the school community.</p>
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				school community.	
PHASE 3: EVALUATION					
OBJECTIVES:	COURSES OF ACTION	BUDGET ALLOCATION	RESOURCES	IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	EXPECTED OUTCOME
<p>a. Ensure training programs match with business goals and educational requirements;</p> <p>b. Assess training programs' efficacy in enhancing participant knowledge, skills, and behaviors;</p> <p>c. Evaluate the impact of training on organizational performance and school governance;</p> <p>d. Gather participant input to identify strengths and areas for development in training programs; and</p>	Total duration: 2 months	25,000Php	<p>Technical Working Committee :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Division Superintendents - Asst. School Division Superintendents - Public Schools District Supervisors - Education Program Supervisors - Resource person/Field Experts <p>Resources: Philippine Professional Standard for School Heads (PPSSH)</p>	<p>Pre-training Assessment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct baseline surveys and evaluations to determine the beginning levels of knowledge, skills, and behaviors. 2. Identify the participants' individual requirements and expectations prior to the training. <p>During Training Evaluation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor progress and engagement using formative evaluation approaches such as observation, feedback forms, and real-time evaluations. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improved training programs to better fit with business goals and participant needs. 2. Improved quality of training content, materials, and delivery methods. 3. Effective training programs lead to improved organizational performance and school governance outcomes. 4. Established a culture of continual learning and development throughout the organization. 5. Improving training programs through systematic evaluation and feedback.

e. Make practical recommendations to improve the success of future training projects.			Long-term Impact Assessment: 1. Follow-up surveys and performance measurements will be used to assess the long-term impact of training programs on organizational performance and school governance.	
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CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations regarding the resilient leadership competencies of school administrators and its effect on organizational performance and governance.

Summary of Findings

Problem 1: Leadership Competencies of School Administrators

It can be noted that the overall assessment of leadership competencies got an often rating as evidenced by 4.84 mean percentage score. This was specified in the leadership competencies, namely, advising, managing, leading, and relating. The leadership competency of advising got an often rating as evidenced by 4.84 mean percentage score. This was specified through these indicators: providing counsel and advise (4.84), directing individuals or groups (4.84), guiding teachers through developmental programs (4.88), practicing active and effective listening skills (4.95), providing opportunities for teachers development (5.00), providing programs equipping individuals to cope with problems (4.73), opening opportunities (4.61), developing teacher to become leaders (4.86), and articulating value of self-leadership (4.86).

Moreover, it can be noted that the overall assessment of leadership competencies in terms of managing got an often rating as evidenced by 4.87 mean percentage score. This was specified through these indicators: full understanding of institution's thrust (4.91), exhibiting knowledge and understanding of school policies (4.93), translating school's vision and mission (4.91), demonstrating ability to implement school policies and programs (4.95), demonstrating basic skills in managing and conflict (4.64), demonstrating ability to manage conflicts (4.96), displaying knowledge in approaching conflict (4.86), and guiding towards commitment to a safe, caring, and nurturing environment (4.80).

Additionally, it can be noted that the overall assessment of leadership competencies in terms of leading got an often rating as evidenced by 4.87 mean percentage

score. This was specified through these indicators: manifesting subordination of personal needs and wants (4.79), articulating principles and essence of teamwork (4.93), developing partnerships and alliances (4.93), responding to the needs of teachers and employees (4.77), displaying a strong foundation of values and qualities of a resonant leader (4.84), exhibiting ability to devote time and energy to lead others (4.91), and exhibiting the ability to show awareness of one's limitations (4.89). Lastly, the leadership competency of relating got an often rating as evidenced by 4.79 mean percentage score.

This was specified by the following indicators: demonstrating responsibility, accountability, maturity, and consistency that leads to the development of trusting relationship (4.64), showing understanding of the requirements for social cohesion (4.90), manifesting self-awareness, empathy, and effective interpretation of emotional and motivational states of others (4.64), helping others to transform through role-modeling (4.95), showing basic knowledge of human behavior and human psychology (4.77), showing sensitivity to other's feeling (4.73), demonstrating skills to use written, spoken, and non-verbal languages (4.86), demonstrating willingness to communicate (4.80), providing avenue for healthy dialogue (4.70), and exhibiting effective listening skill (4.89).

Problem 2: Level of Resilience of School Leaders

It can be noted in the overall assessment of the school leader's resiliency got a highly resilient rating as evidence by 3.70 mean percentage score. This was specified through the following indicators: able to adapt to changes (3.59), having a secure relationship (3.68), seeking help from God (3.68), dealing with whatever comes along the way (3.54), looking for confidence from the past successes (3.43), seeing the humorous side of the problem (3.52), coping from stress (3.54), bouncing back after illness, injury, or other hardship (3.61), believing that things happens for a reason (3.66), giving effort no matter the outcome (3.71), believing of achieving goals despite obstacles (3.98), not giving up even in hopelessness (3.79), knowing where to turn for help during times of crisis/stress (3.66), staying focused despite under pressure (3.80), prefer to take the lead in solving problems (3.71), not being easily discouraged by failures (3.84), being strong in dealing

with life's challenges and difficulties (3.73), making difficult decision (3.66), able to handle unpleasant and painful feelings (3.66), dealing with life's problems (3.77), having a strong sense of purpose (3.89), feeling control of life (3.66), liking challenges (3.88), working to attain goals (3.61), and taking pride of achievement (3.88).

Problem 3: Primary Challenges Identified by the School Administrators

The study on challenges faced by school administrators revealed a complex issue that impacts school governance. The challenges brought by the COVID-19 emerged as a primary concern among school administrators. The said challenges posed a disruption on traditional learning and sudden swift to remote and online learning modalities. Additionally, administrators dealt with the consequences of budget issues, teacher shortage, and damages caused by a heavy storm and flooding in the school community. Instances of teacher misconduct, bomb threat and safety concerns posed an obstacle in fostering a child-friendly school environment which prompts school administrators to address disciplinary issued and prioritizing students' safety and well-being.

Problem 4: Common Themes and Findings Found in the Convergence of Data Presented

The most prevailing response is resilience. This leadership quality encourages adaptability and empowers both school leaders and teachers to respond to unexpected challenges. Resilience is important in the success of school organization. School leaders must be adaptable to regulate strategies and approaches in creating a more resilient school environment. Good decision-making is also notable. Respondents believes that decision making skills of school leaders are essential in maintaining resilience which strengthens the school organization.

Clear communication was highlighted as well by the respondents. It supposes that effective communication skills are one of the important qualities of a school leader. This promotes trust and collaboration among school and community members. The impact of communication significantly creates solidarity among school leaders, teachers, students, and stakeholders. Empowering teachers was also highlighted in the converged data which

emphasized the role of school administrators to provide support, resources, and professional development opportunities to empower teachers.

Problem 5: Effects of School Administrators' Leadership Competencies in the Resilience in Organizational Performance and Governance

Results of the regression analysis indicates that the 4 variables of leadership competencies of school leaders significantly affect the resilience in organizational performance and governance to a different extent as shown by the .002 coefficients. The table of coefficients shows that the B coefficients represents change in the dependent variable for a one-unit change in the independent variable. Advising increases one-unit in the independent variable corresponds to a .111 unit increase in the dependent variable. The B coefficient of Advising (.111) suggests that it has a positive effect on the outcome. Similarly, Managing B coefficient .054 implies a positive effect of managing on the outcome. However, Leading (-.060) and Relating (-.007) B-coefficients suggest negative effect on the outcome. Looking at the t-statistics and their respective associated p values can conclude that among the four competencies, .358 (advising).665 (managing), .534 (leading), and .938 (relating) are found to be statistically significant since is greater than the alpha value of .05.

Analysis of the sustained Beta coefficients would reveal that of four (4) variables of leadership competencies of school leaders, advising, managing, leading, and relating appeared to be the best predictors of resilience in the resilience of organizational performance and governance.

Results of the analysis of variance of the regression of leadership competencies for school leaders revealed an F-value of .360 with a p-value of .002. Since that the associated probability exceed .05 alpha, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, safe to conclude that the combined effects of Leadership Competencies namely Advising, Managing, Leading, and Relating form a set of predictors on the Resilience in Organizational Performance and Governance.

Problem 6: Training Program Sustaining Effective Organizational Performance and School Governance

Every organization aspires to be successful through differentiated programs, services, seminars, and trainings. There is no doubt that a well-trained and developed employees will be effective to the organization and will increase the changes of their efficiency in performing their duties and responsibilities. These developmental programs are specific frameworks for helping employees develop their skills, knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and consequently improve their abilities to perform specific tasks in the workplace (Karim et al., 2019). In establishing a training program for sustaining organizational performance and governance, the researcher proposes the followings stages, namely: Training Plan and Development, Implementation, and Evaluation.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The leadership competencies of school leaders are generally high. A high level of assessment was attributed to advising, managing, leading, and relating competencies which is an indication that school leaders are deemed to be necessary in the effective and efficient in school governance.
2. The level of resilience of respondents notably high, especially on believing in achieving goals despite of obstacles, having a strong purpose in life, liking challenges, and taking pride in their achievements. The findings indicate that school leaders strong and capable when facing challenges. School leaders also demonstrate a high level of optimism and self-efficacy allowing them to bounce back and continue pursuing their goals.
3. School leaders build resilience to address challenges which helped tremendously in responding to change. Resilience building helped school leaders not only in managing crises but also in improving organizational performance and governance. Decision-making skills and clear communication are essential in maintaining resilience in the organization and promoting trust and collaboration among community members. Furthermore,

School leaders must be adaptable to regulate strategies and approaches in creating a more resilient school environment.

4. The four (4) variable of leadership competencies of school leaders appeared to be best predictors of resilience in organization performance and governance. The results suggest that leadership competencies school leaders influence the resilience in organizational performance and governance.

Recommendations

Based on the results and the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Implement Continuing Professional Development programs that focus on advanced leadership theories, innovative management strategies, and emerging trends in education. This would allow school leaders to stay update with the latest trends and educational practices, continuous learning, and development.
2. Catastrophes are inevitable. Offer resilience training workshop designed for principals and school leaders in detail to maintain the resilience and well-being of school leaders. Promote a culture of continuous learning within the Division of Malolos highlighting strong practices in maintaining resilience among school leaders.
3. Conduct a regular assessment on leadership capabilities among the principals and school leaders within the Division of Malolos. Develop targeted training and development programs to enhance leadership capacity.
4. Develop and implement resilience training programs tailored to the needs of principals and school leaders focusing on enhancing skills such as problem-solving, decision-making, adaptability, and effective communication. Figure 4 present the proposed comprehensive training program (PPA) on Leadership, Resilience, and Effective School Governance training aims to enhance the leadership capabilities of school administrators. Topics of this training include

strategic planning, team building, communication skills, conflict resolution, instructional leadership, and fostering a positive school climate.

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APPENDIX A RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale 25 (CD-RISC-25) ©

For each item, please mark an "x" in the box below that best indicates how much you agree with the following statements as they apply to you over the last month. If a particular situation has not occurred recently, answer according to how you think you would have felt.

	not true at all (0)	rarely true (1)	sometim es true (2)	often true (3)	true nearly all the time (4)
1. I am able to adapt when changes occur.	<input type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I have at least one close and secure relationship that helps me when I am stressed.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. When there are no clear solutions to my problems, sometimes fate or God can help.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. I can deal with whatever comes my way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Past successes give me confidence in dealing with new challenges and difficulties.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Good or bad, I believe that most things happen for a reason.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. I give my best effort no matter what the outcome may be.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12. Even when things look hopeless, I don't give up.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13. During times of stress/crisis, I know where to turn for help.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14. Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15. I prefer to take the lead in solving problems rather than letting others make all the decisions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16. I am not easily discouraged by failure.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17. I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18. I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people, if it is necessary.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
19. I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
20. In dealing with life's problems, sometimes you have to act on a hunch without knowing why.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
21. I have a strong sense of purpose in life.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
22. I feel in control of my life.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23. I like challenges.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
24. I work to attain my goals no matter what roadblocks I encounter along the way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
25. I take pride in my achievements.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add up your score for each column 0 + ___ + ___ + ___ + ___

Add each of the column totals to obtain CD-RISC score = _____

**Adapted from Connor-Davidson (2003), Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) Manual.*

COMPETENCY EVALUATION TOOL FOR SCHOOL LEADERS

Developed by Henry G. Magat, EdD

(Copyright 2014)

This instrument is designed to assess your level of competency in the following areas, deemed to be necessary in effective and efficient school leaders. Kindly review the following categories and rate your degree of competency by checking the column using the scale below:

5 – Very sufficient 4 – Quite sufficient 3 – Sufficient 2 – Little 1 - None

CATEGORY 1: ADVISING

The Advising competency area includes the knowledge, skills and attitudes related to developing a high level of professional standards of quality counseling, coaching, and providing support and direction. This also includes the understanding and application of theories, principles, and concepts of student development.

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
1.1 The ability to inspire through Mentoring					
As a school leader, I:					
1.1.1 provide counsel or advice to individuals and groups that lead to better self-realization.					
1.1.2 direct individual and groups through processes that hone their skills to deal effectively with personal, educational, and social concerns.					
1.1.3 guide the students through developmental programs that will provide life-long learning.					
1.1.4 practice active and effective listening skills.					

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
1.2 The ability to hone student potentials for leadership					
As school leader, I:					
1.2.1 provide opportunities for individual students to improve their leadership skills and potentials through participation in student activities, organizations, developmental programs and trainings toward their total well-being.					
1.2.2 provide programs that will equip individuals to cope with personal, educational, and social problems through exposure to real life situation.					
1.2.3 open opportunities to integrate with other members of the school community to better understand cultures and diversity.					
1.2.4 develop individual students to become confident, self-directed, effective, and ethical leaders.					
1.2.5 articulate the value of self-leadership and self-management.					

CATEGORY 2: MANAGING

Description

The Managing competency area includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for the realization of the vision, mission, and core values of the institution. This also includes understanding of the basic principles that underlie conflict in organizations and facilitating the resolution of these conflicts.

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
2.1 The ability to integrate the school’s philosophical framework with job responsibilities and to educate the school community on current legal issues concerning students.					

School leaders should be able to:					
2.1.1 Show full understanding of the institution’s thrust through its vision, mission, and core values.					
2.1.2 Exhibit knowledge and understanding of school policy in relation with laws and jurisprudence concerning students.					
2.1.3 Translate the school’s vision-mission into programs and activities that will involve individuals and groups.					
2.1.4 Demonstrate ability to implement school policies and programs that are congruent with institutional vision and strategic plans.					

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
2.2 The ability to manage and resolve conflicts.					
School leaders should be able to:					
2.2.1 Demonstrate basic skills in managing conflict and focusing on resolution, building trust, and establishing rapport.					
2.2.2 Demonstrate ability to manage conflicts by leading individuals or groups to a practical, effective, and fair resolution.					
2.2.3 Display knowledge in approaching conflict, such as analysis of the issues and interests at stake, cause of the conflict, opportunity of both sides to be heard, and objective resolution of the issue.					
2.2.4 Guide towards commitment to a safe, caring, and nurturing environment.					

CATEGORY 3: LEADING

Description

The Leading competency area includes the knowledge, skills and abilities required of a leader to work effectively, to envision, to plan, to effect change, and to address issues in and out of the organization. This also includes subordination of personal agenda, and observance of ethical practice at work.

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
3.1 The ability to understanding his/her role and responsibilities which transcend to a sense of vocation.					
School leaders should be able to:					
1.1.1 Manifest subordination of personal needs and wants to the higher objectives and principles.					
1.1.2 Articulate principles and essence of teamwork that focus on organizational success rather than on personal interest					
3.1.3 Develop partnerships and alliances in spite of differences and diverse values and principles.					
3.1.4 Respond to the needs of students and employees over and above self-interest.					

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
3.2 The ability to embed Values and to observe Ethical principles in the practice of educational leadership.					
School leaders should be able to:					
3.2.1 Display a strong foundation of values and qualities of a resonant leader.					
3.2.2 Exhibit the ability to devote time and energy to leading the process of enabling others to clarify					

their personal core values that will serve as the basis of their decision-making.					
3.2.3 Show awareness of one’s limitations by recognizing the need for the supervision and guidance of others.					

CATEGORY 4: RELATING

Description

The Relating competency area includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to interact with individuals and groups with diverse views. This also includes the needed communication competence of a school leader.

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
4.1 The ability to maintain and manage Interpersonal Relationship					
School leaders should be able to:					
1.1.1 Demonstrate responsibility, accountability, maturity, and consistent propensity for transparency that leads to the development of trusting relationships.					
1.1.2 Show understanding of the requirements for social cohesion, such as respect for and appreciation of values, beliefs, identity, biases, heritage, cultures, and histories of others that create an inclusive environment.					
1.1.3 Manifest self-awareness, empathy, and effective interpretation of underlying emotional and motivational states of others.					
1.1.4 Help others to transform through role-modeling.					
1.1.5 Show basic knowledge of human behavior and human psychology that is useful to identify ways to address students concerns.					
1.1.6 Show sensitivity to others’ feelings.					

Key Competencies	5	4	3	2	1
4.2 The ability to Communicate effectively to stakeholders of the school community					
School leaders should be able to:					
1.2.1 Demonstrate skills to use written, spoken, and non-verbal languages, efficiently and effectively.					
1.2.2 Demonstrate willingness to communicate with people in their level that result in effective information exchange.					
1.2.3 Provide an avenue for a healthy dialogue with students, parents, and other concerned individuals in or out of the organization.					
1.2.4 Exhibit effective listening skill that leads to a better understanding of complex ideas and situations.					

**Adapted from the study of Magat (2019), Evaluation Tool Development for Student Affairs and Services Practitioners: A Phenomenological Study.*

APPENDIX J
Role of Leadership in Developing Resilience in School/Organization

Meaning Unit	Condensed Meaning Unit	Subtheme	Theme
<p><i>Fostering resilience within the school environment is a practice in our school to withstand challenges as I may always face as the school head. The performance of our organization is a must for me to achieve the overall effectiveness of each individual employee who is serving in our school, our workplace. (A1)</i></p>	<p>The participant prioritizes fostering resiliency to help them address challenges that may arise which ensures effective performance of all employees.</p>	<p>Encouraging resilience</p>	<p>Resilience building</p>
<p><i>School leaders must be a role model in presenting resiliency by demonstrating leadership abilities in the face of difficulty, internal and external problems in school organization. (F1)</i></p>	<p>School leaders should demonstrate resiliency that showcase a strong leadership ability.</p>	<p>Demonstrating resilience</p>	

<p><i>Leadership is essential in fostering resilience within the school climate, first and foremost, as it sets the example for how our staff and students will respond and prevail over challenges. (C1)</i></p>	<p>Leadership plays an important role in cultivating resilience. The participant demonstrates the role of leadership in promoting resilience.</p>	<p>Developing resilient organization</p>	
<p><i>As a school head, the ability of a school leader to successfully manage crises and uncertainties is important developing resilience in school community. (H1)</i></p>	<p>Crisis management is an important leadership skill and in cultivating resilience in school community.</p>	<p>Managing crises</p>	
<p><i>As a school leader, modeling within and building confidence can withstand the challenges and has impact in the organizational performance. (B1)</i></p>	<p>The participant inspires confidence to endure challenges which in turn leads to improved organizational performance.</p>	<p>Encouraging self-confidence</p>	<p>Leadership development</p>

<p><i>As a school head, leadership is important in fostering resilience in schools, first and foremost, as it sets the example for how our teachers and students will respond and overcome challenges. (D1)</i></p>	<p>The participant sets an example on responding and prevailing over challenges.</p>	<p>Setting example</p>	
<p><i>Resilient leadership encourages teachers and non-teaching personnel a culture of cooperation and teamwork. It will also courage them to help one another. (G1)</i></p>	<p>Resilient leadership develop a culture of cooperation and teamwork that encourages mutual support and assistance.</p>	<p>Promoting collaboration</p>	
<p><i>As a school principal, I instill confidence and trust in our teachers to create a feeling of empowerment to successfully overcome challenges. (E1)</i></p>	<p>The participant fosters trust and confidence among teachers which empowers them to effectively overcome problems in school organization.</p>	<p>Empowering teachers</p>	<p>Teacher empowerment</p>
<p><i>As a school principal, I've come to realize the important role of resilience. Leadership</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participant learned the vital role of resilience in leadership. 	<p>Developing resilience</p>	

<p><i>is the foundation upon which resilience is formed within your organization. Resilient leaders foster a development mentality among its teachers and learners/students. (II)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Leadership is essential to building resilience in organization and it cultivates a growth mindset among teachers and students.		
<p><i>School leaders that value resilience promotes teachers' professional development. Leaders must know that a well-supported teaching workforce is better prepared to face difficulties. (J1)</i></p>	<p>Resilient leaders develop teacher's professional growth, recognizing that a well-supported teachers are more equipped in overcoming challenges.</p>	<p>Teachers' development</p>	

APPENDIX K
Impact of Leadership Qualities

Meaning Unit	Condensed Meaning Unit	Subtheme	Theme
<p><i>Adaptable to changes, a leader must be transformational, visionary also, focus the vision (there's a dream to reach and to make it in reality).</i> (A2)</p>	<p>A leader must be adaptable, transformational, and visionary.</p>	<p>Adaptive leader</p>	<p>Adaptability</p>
<p><i>In leadership, adaptability is important because it enables leaders and teachers to change strategies and approaches faced with different conditions to build an even more resilient school environment. (D2)</i></p>	<p>Adaptability is important in regulating strategies and approaches in creating a more resilient school environment.</p>	<p>Importance of adaptability</p>	
<p><i>I believe that adaptability allows schools leaders and teachers to adapt flexibility to every unexpected problem. Encouraging sense of</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participant believes that adaptability empowers school leaders and teachers to respond to 	<p>Adaptability and resilience</p>	

<p><i>resilience in dealing with difficulties is also important achieving a successful school organization. (H2)</i></p>	<p>unexpected challenges.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging resilience is important in the success of school organization. 		
<p><i>Adaptability is a vital leadership quality in the promotion of resilience in our employees and teachers. It helps us to determine the challenges to address them effectively. (C2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability is important in encouraging teachers to be resilient since it improve ways in determining ways to address problems. 	<p>Adaptability in determining solutions</p>	
<p><i>I believe that the decision-making abilities of school leaders is very important in sustaining resilience. Resilient leaders must be confident since it may reduce the effects of problems encountered in schools. (E2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participant believes that decision making skills of school leaders are essential in maintaining resilience. • Confidence in making decision can reduce effects of problem leaders faced in schools. 	<p>Decision-making skills</p>	<p>Decision-making</p>

<p><i>I believe as a leader that one of the important qualities of a school leader is decision-making skills because it strengthens the resiliency of the entire school organization. (I2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The respondent believes that one of the important qualities of a school leader is decision-making skills as it strengthens the school organization. 	<p>Decision-making skills</p>	
<p><i>Strong decision making and critical thinking abilities provide a clear direction and strong strategic plan. These qualities allow leaders to navigate complicated circumstances confidently and decisively. These qualities of a good leader articulate a convincing vision for the future. (J2)</i></p>	<p>Strong decision making and critical thinking skills shows a clear direction and strong strategic plan, allowing leaders to navigate complex situations with confidence and decisiveness articulating convincing vision.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<p>Decision making and critical thinking skills</p>	
<p><i>Resilience develops visionary leadership which gives a sense of purpose and direction.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resilience develops visionary leaders by providing 	<p>Vision and sense of Purpose</p>	

<p><i>It also encourages administrators and teachers to persevere in times of uncertainties. (F3)</i></p>	<p>purpose and direction.</p>		
<p><i>Clear communication among community members promoting shared vision and mission that will drive positive outcomes. (B2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communication among members to promote shared vision and mission 	<p>Impact of communication</p>	<p>Sense of purpose/direction</p>
<p><i>I believe that one of the important qualities of a school head or principal is communication. Effective communication creates trust and collaboration among the members of school organization which results in a supportive community like one big family. (G2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants believes that effective communication is an important quality of a school leader. • Effective communication promotes trust and collaboration among school members which creates a community that supports one another. 	<p>Effective communication</p>	

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, occupying the central portion of the page. This area is typically used for students to provide answers or show their work during an exam.